

Deliverable report for

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling

Project 101058632

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WP / Task
All WPs and Tasks

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2 ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

Acronym	Description
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan (for START)
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
ExCom	START's Executive Committee (WP leaders)
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KoM	Kick-off meeting
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
WP	Work Package
PM	Powder Metallurgy
TEG	ThermoElectric Generators
MTOD	Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination
URL	Uniform Resource Locator

3 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present deliverable reports on the activity of WP6 “Dissemination and Communication” in the period 1st December 2022 – 31st May 2023¹ (M07-M12 of the START project).

It covers the endeavours within the following tasks (the ones running in said period):

- Task 6.1: Specific project dissemination and communication tools
- Task 6.2: Technical and scientific dissemination
- Task 6.4: Clustering

During the period, 2 deliverables (this D6.4, and D6.5 concerning Training activities) were achieved in WP6 and reported. The activities for D&C, that are reported in this deliverable, include:

- Updates to the START project website.
- Updates on the Social Media accounts (LinkedIn, YouTube, Twitter, Twitch, SlideShare).
- The second issue of the public biannual newsletter “RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE”.
- 2 free webinars, in February and April (and one on 31st May) mainly on topics linked to minerals and raw materials, have been organised, with good participation.
- Publications on widespread technical magazines, namely Powder Metallurgy Review, água&ambiente, and Ingenium.
- Dissemination at events: PDAC in Canada, two consortium partners General Assemblies, and a Green Transition conference in Sweden. Other events will be covered during next months.

The KPIs set for the D&C activities have mostly been met (not considering those that have a longer deadline), with the exception of Twitter, although the results in terms of views there seem to suggest that the original goal was probably unnecessary.

The clustering activity has continued. Contacts with some key projects and stakeholders have started, and START may join an existing cluster of other projects.

¹ For practical reasons linked to text reviewing and submission, some details related to the last 2 weeks of May could not be reported and will be dealt with in the next deliverable of the same series, D6.6 (M18).

4 INTRODUCTION: STRUCTURE OF WP6 AND GENERAL PLAN OF ACTIVITIES

4.1 OBJECTIVES OF WP6

The overall objective of WP6 is to disseminate widely the results of the START project in order to maximise its impact. The key objectives are:

- To raise awareness of all relevant parties (scientific and industrial communities, general public and policy makers) about START project activities in a coherent and consistent manner.
- To ensure an effective dissemination of the technical and scientific results of START project to the scientific and industrial communities.
- To ensure an effective communication of the achievements of START project to the wider scientific and technical communities, policy makers and the general public.
- To elaborate the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) and update it when required.

Various communication activities are envisaged to disseminate the on-going and final project findings:

- Participations in congresses, workshops, webinars
- Training events
- Websites and social media
- Scientific papers
- Newsletters and other publications
- Participation in trade fairs and exhibitions
- Other activities, etc.

All partners are required to collaborate in dissemination and communication by delivering content and executing some dissemination subtasks.

4.2 STRUCTURE OF WP6

4.2.1 Tasks

The activity is organised in 5 Tasks, whose scope and activities will be explained in the main chapters of this report.

- Task 6.1: Specific project dissemination and communication tools
- Task 6.2: Technical and scientific dissemination
- Task 6.3: Training activities
- Task 6.4: Clustering
- Task 6.5: Final event

The GANTT of shows the start and end of each task. As can be seen, only Tasks 6.1, 6.2 and 6.4 have already begun, whereas task 6.3 is due to start in a few months and Task 6.5 only in Year 4, rather close to the end of the project.

Figure 1: GANTT chart for WP6. M01 = June 2022; M48 = May 2026.

4.2.2 Deliverables and Milestones

The WP lists 15 deliverables out of a total of 39 for the whole project, but only one milestone, that has already been achieved in M03 (August 2022). The deliverables, also visible in Figure 3, can be grouped in the following categories:

- D6.1 - Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools (M02): This deliverable describes the project's website, addresses the inherent need of the project to develop the START graphical identity, together with all the other online tools designed to support objectives of WP6. *(Submitted and approved)*
- D6.2 - Dissemination and Communication Plan (M03): Document outlining the most efficient strategy and means for implementing the dissemination and communication activities. *(Submitted)*
- D6.3, D6.4, D6.6, D6.7, D6.9, D6.10, D6.12, D6.13 - Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities (M06, M12, M18, M24, M30, M36, M42, M48): Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis, describing all the dissemination, communication, outreach and clustering activities with other EU projects and initiatives that have been developed and implemented and plans on how to proceed. *(D6.4 is the present report, D6.6 upcoming in 6 months)*
- D6.5, D6.8, D6.11, D6.14 - Training activities (M12, M24, M36, M48): Report on a 12-month basis describing the training activities implemented. *(D6.5 submitted, D6.8 upcoming in 12 months)*
- D6.15 - Final Event (M46): Final event conference report.

Concerning milestones, only one was envisaged, namely Milestone 08:

- MS08: Project Website (M03) - Project website functional and accessible

The website was in fact the key stone of all further dissemination, so it needed to be started as early as possible and was set as a milestone. This milestone has been achieved as planned (declared on 22 August 2022 on the Funding & Tenders Portal, the website being also subject of Deliverable D6.1 submitted earlier and already accepted).

Deliverables												
Work Package No	Deliverable Related No	Deliverable No	Deliverable Name	Description	Lead Beneficiary	Type	Dissemination Level	Due Date	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date	Approval Date	Status
WP6	D6.1	D19	Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools	This deliverable describes the project's we	EPMA	DEC	PU	31 Jul 2022		29 Jul 2022	31 Aug 2022	Approved
WP6	D6.2	D20	Dissemination and Communication Plan	Document outlining the most efficient strat	EPMA	R	PU	31 Aug 2022		30 Aug 2022		Submitted
WP6	D6.3	D21	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M6	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2022		30 Nov 2022		Submitted
WP6	D6.4	D22	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M12	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2023				Pending
WP6	D6.5	D23	Training activities - M12	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basi	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2023				Pending
WP6	D6.6	D24	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M18	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2023				Pending
WP6	D6.7	D25	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M24	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.8	D26	Training activities - M24	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basi	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.9	D27	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M30	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2024				Pending
WP6	D6.10	D28	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M36	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.11	D29	Training activities - M36	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basi	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.12	D30	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M42	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	30 Nov 2025				Pending
WP6	D6.13	D31	Dissemination, outreach and clustering activities - M48	Report to be prepared on a 6-month basis	EPMA	R	PU	31 May 2026				Pending
WP6	D6.14	D32	Training activities - M48	Report to be prepared on a 12-month basi	ASGMI	R	PU	31 May 2026				Pending
WP6	D6.15	D33	Final Event	Final event conference report.	ASGMI	R	PU	31 Mar 2026				Pending
			To be completed on the current year									
			Deadline approaching									
			Submitted									
			Approved									

Figure 2: List of WP6 deliverables, with deadlines and status.

5 TASK 6.1: SPECIFIC PROJECT DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION TOOLS

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M01 to M48

The objective of this task is to develop tools and produce materials that will be used during and after the project to disseminate the information about the project, its partners, and its results. According to our proposal, these were the items that needed to be developed:

- The Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) at the start of the project and updated when required.
- The Project's Graphical Identity (logo, branding).
- The START project website.
- A special area on the EPMA website (www.epma.com) devoted to the START project.
- Social Media platforms, in particular:
 - A LinkedIn page for networking with the professional community (managed by EPMA).
 - A YouTube profile for engaging with the greater public (managed by EPMA).
 - A Twitter account for business and policy makers (managed by LPRC).
 - A Twitch profile for engagement with young people (managed by LPRC).
 - A SlideShare account for disseminating project presentations globally (managed by ASGMI).
- Leaflets, posters, banners, branded consumables that will be used as advertising material to be distributed in digital and/or physical versions.
- A public biannual newsletter to be distributed in digital and/or physical versions.
- A serious game (see WP7, Task 7.1 and deliverable D7.2)
- Videos about the project (2 generic videos, 1 at the start and one at the end, 3 more focused videos on specific topics).

The tools had been further described in the original proposal as in Table 1.

Table 1: Tools for Dissemination and Communication as indicated in the proposal.

Tool	Purpose	Audience	Due	Quantified target
Project Identity	Graphical A Graphical Identity for the START project (logo and general branding colour schemes, for the website, the social media, mail signatures for partners, and all other uses) will be developed in the first months.	All	M02	-
Project website	Main channel for information and major tool for the visibility of the START activities. Updated frequently, with a blend of status, push and active content, including: project overview; public documents; agenda; articles and news; multimedia. Individuals can also use the website to sign up to the newsletter and social media channels.	All groups	M02 onwards	Visitors: 2000 in year 1 rising to at least 4000 in year 4
Social media	LinkedIn, YouTube and Twitter will be considered as main dissemination channels, Slideshare and Twitch as secondary dissemination channels. LinkedIn supports community management with restricted fora. A YouTube channel will be used to engage with a broader audience by sharing videos, including an introduction to START, short interviews, and selected partner videos.	All groups	M02 onwards	Twitter: 1000 followers in year 1, rising to 2500 by the end of the project LinkedIn: 800 followers by the end of the project.
Videos	Some videos are planned for various uses: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A short generic video (0.5-1 min) with simple information, to be used for general awareness about START. • A mid-term longer video, highlighting preliminary project results. • 2 or more short videos focused on different subtopics within the project, with examples of improvements achieved within the project. • A short generic video (0.5-1 min) with simple information, to be used as a summary of the results obtained in START. 	Groups 1-4 1-3 2-3 1-4	M04 M24 M48 M48	Average of 200 views per video (at least 100 total views)
Newsletters	A public biannual newsletter will be circulated to individuals who sign up. The newsletter will include a summary of the activities over a 6-month period.	Groups 1-3	M06 onwards	Demand led but minimum of 500 per semester
Webinars/ seminars/ workshop	Communication of the project outcomes and activities, to share knowledge, ideas and updates.	Groups 2, 3	M06 onwards	Audience of 100 per event
Serious online game	A serious online game for capacity building on raw materials, sustainability and circular economy.	All groups	M24 onwards	Visitors: 300
Other publications	Articles on web-based innovation news services, like the Horizon Magazine, Cordis, and on commercial magazines like Open Access Management	All groups	M06 onwards	Total reach >400000

Most of these tools have already been developed following the schedule and the details have been given in the previous deliverables. New achievements will be described in the next pages.

5.1 DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN

The Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP) has been already developed and reported in deliverable D6.2 (“Dissemination and Communication Plan”), submitted on 30th August 2022. The DCP, in its initial version, leads the activity on Dissemination and Communication also in relationship with the other WPs, and will be updated during the project (at least at M24 and M48) to guarantee flexibility and optimisation of D&C efforts, as measured via the selected KPIs.

The DCP contains an outline of all the activities envisaged within the project for D&C, including the various procedures for publications, to monitor the performance of the D&C effort, etc.

It is a very comprehensive document that has been thoroughly described in D6.2: for this reason, we are not going to describe it again here in detail. For the sake of readability of this report, we will just list here the subchapters in which the DCP is divided.

1. Target audience segmentation
2. Events
3. Rules for Publication
 - 3.1. Deliverables
 - 3.2. General publications
 - 3.3. Publications on project website
 - 3.4. Publications on project's social media
 - 3.5. Publications on external media – magazines, journals, presentations in events
4. Project Graphical Identity
5. Project Website
6. Social Media
7. START Newsletter
8. Videos
9. Webinars / Seminars / Workshops
10. Scientific Publications and Participation to Scientific Events
11. Other Publications
12. Participation in Industrial Events
13. Participation in other Events
14. Materials for booths/physical distribution
 - 14.1. Leaflet(s)
 - 14.2. Roller banner(s)
 - 14.3. Poster(s)
 - 14.4. Consumables
15. Serious Online Game
16. START comics
17. Training
 - 17.1. START lectures during the EPMA PM Summer School
 - 17.2. ASGMI workshops
 - 17.3. Final Training Workshop
18. Clustering
19. Continuous Evaluation of D&C Performance
 - 19.1. KPIs
 - 19.2. WP6 meetings
 - 19.3. Continuous reporting on Funding & Tender website
20. Update of the DCP

The preparation of the DCP took several weeks in July/August 2022, and involved many of the partners, in particular those included in the project's ExCom. The text was collected by EPMA.

5.2 TARGET AUDIENCE SEGMENTATION

As written in the DCP, the audience for the project topics has been and will be segmented in 4 groups, depending on their role and possible interactivity with the project:

- **Group 1** - Policy makers and influencers concerned with the green transition and sustainable circular economy at European level. This group includes, local, regional, country and EU level political figures, especially those in charge and influential in all relevant policies concerning

industry, minerals and mining, energy, supply chains, sustainability, and potentially all journalists, web- or print-based, all social media (LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube) influential people dealing with scientific, mining, resources, industrial, energy and sustainability topics.

- **Group 2** - Economically active entrepreneurs and industrial actors at European level in the three main segments of the value chain:
 - a. Raw material suppliers (mining sector)
 - b. TEG device producers (thermoelectric industry)
 - c. TEG utilisers (i.e., waste heat producers)
- **Group 3** - Scientific community across the geology, materials science, thermoelectric energy harvesting, renewable energy
- **Group 4** – General public across the EU

For maximum efficacy, the D&C activities will have to address each target groups with the correct approach (scientific/technical/non-technical/emotional, impact, economic features, and language tuned to the media).

In the first part of the project, D&C efforts have to use only limited material that is the basic project concept and some general information on the scientific and application background of the materials, technologies and devices that are of interest for the project. Therefore, Group 3 was hardly approachable, and only at a “superficial” level, as no foreground has yet been developed. On the other hand, most activities have been general (website, LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube), so potentially reaching all groups. Other activities in events were basically oriented towards group 2 or group 3 (but as explained with not very technical information).

5.3 PROJECT WEBSITE

The project’s website has been already developed and reported in deliverable D6.1 (“Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools”), submitted on 29th July 2022. It also constituted the criterion for the achievement of Milestone MS08 (“Project Website (M03) - Project website functional and accessible”), that was declared achieved on 22nd August 2022.

The website address is

www.START-HEproject.com

Another site address, www.HE-START.eu, is automatically redirected to the main address.

The website is continually updated in terms of contents and new features are introduced (new pages, widgets, etc.) if deemed useful.

In fact, since the first development of the website, shown in the mentioned D6.1, some more documents and news have been published on it, and some modifications in the pages has been carried out.

On the “Documents” page, there are now 9 documents for download (Figure 4) in addition to the 7 already documented in D6.3. The new additions are:

- “Starty explains START, multilingual edition”,
- The Newsletter Issue #2 (see chapter 5.5.2).

More documents will be made available in the future.

Figure 4: Updated Documents page (screenshot taken on 22/05/2023).

The “News” page is the page that had more additions, as it was used to convey the info about the events and the news about the project (Figure 5). The details can be found on the website itself, each piece of news opens a specific page. As an example, only the page about the selection of the Scientific Advisory Board is given here (Figure 6).

Figure 5: The updated News page (screenshot taken on 22/05/2023).

START Home The Project Documents News Methods Consensus Contacts

The Project Scientific Advisory Board has been appointed

Welcome our Scientific Advisory Board members!

Dear Project members, we are pleased to announce the appointment of our Scientific Advisory Board. The Board will provide expert advice and guidance on the scientific aspects of the project, and will meet regularly to discuss the progress of the project and to advise on the most effective ways to achieve our goals.

We are pleased to welcome the following members to the Board:

- Doug Crane**
START Scientific Advisory Board Member
- Jean-yves Erbacher**
START Scientific Advisory Board Member
- Julie Hillis**
START Scientific Advisory Board Member

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Figure 6: The News item about the selection of the Scientific Advisory Board.

In the Multimedia page (Figure 7), more items are now accessible. At the time of D6.3, only the introductory video was there embedded. This is the list of the additions, in order of creation:

- Video of the conference “Como generar electricidad a partir de las escombreras mineras”, in English “How to generate electricity from mining tailings”, given on 10th November 2022 by Ester Boixereu i Vila (IGME-CSIC) during the event called “Semana de la Ciencia y la Innovación” (“Science and Innovation Week”) in Madrid.
- Full recording of the first START webinar, that was held on 28th February 2023, 14:30-15:30 CET.
- Full recording of the second START webinar, that was held on 26th April 2023, 16:00-17:15 CEST.

Please note that a third webinar took place on 31st May 2023, so although it was not possible to document it in this deliverable, it was actually carried out within the covered period and its footage will be embedded here as well.

The “Consortium” page had to be updated in April 2023 due to the change of name and logo by a partner; from “Geological Survey of Austria (GBA)” to “Geosphere Austria” (Figure 8).

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Please check this page for interesting videos and images about the project and its activities!

Here is the full recording of the second START webinar, that was held on 26th April 2023, 16:00 - 17:15 CEST. The event hosted the following presentations:

- "Introductory remarks" - F. Neves (INEC) - Project coordinator
- Freidy Guzmán Martínez, head of Environmental Projects of the Servicio Geológico Mexicano (Mexican Geological Service)
 - "Critical raw materials in mining environmental liabilities: A review"
- Rafael Bizencourt Lima, geologia researcher at CPRM - Serviço Geológico do Brasil (Brazilian Geological Service)
 - "Tetraahedrite as an accessory mineral in Brazilian mineral deposits"

The presentations were followed by a Q&A and discussions.

Share the link to all the colleagues who could be interested in watching the webinar, and keep in touch for the next webinar! Have you already subscribed to our mailing list? You can do it, right now in our "Contact" page!

Here is the full recording of the first START webinar, that was held on 28th February 2023, 14:00 - 15:00 CEST. More than 60 participants attended the event, that hosted two presentations:

- "Overview of the START project" - F. Neves (INEC) - Project coordinator
- "The challenge of collecting uniform samples for use in the START Project" - Daniel P. Silva (CITEVA)

The presentations were followed by a Q&A and discussions.

Share the link to all the colleagues who could be interested in watching the webinar, and keep in touch for the next webinars! Have you already subscribed to our mailing list? You can do it, right now in our "Contact" page!

On 10th November, Ester Bakkerouj Vilu (IGME CSO) gave a presentation in Spanish on the START project at the headquarters of the professional association of Spanish geologists (COG), in Madrid (the conference, whose title in English would be "How to generate electricity from mining tailings", was part of an event called Formosa de la Ciencia y la Innovación (Science and Innovation Week) in Madrid). This week is an event for scientific dissemination and citizen participation organized by the Community of Madrid through the Fundación for Knowledge Madrid whose objective is to actively involve society in research processes and development in science, technology and innovation, and is aimed at the general public. You can watch the presentation here, from the COG YouTube channel.

The thermoelectric materials will be sustainable, coming from EU-sourced ores and recycled wastes, irrespective outside EU.

Do you know what is the scope of the START Project? Just follow our 1st and Starty in this introductory video about the objectives of the project, how we plan to obtain them, and the impact we hope our approach of recycling of mine wastes into thermoelectric devices for energy harvesting will have. Subscribe to our mailing list on the "Contact" page to be kept informed about START.

Tweets from @START_HEproject

START - HE project
@START_HEproject · May 3

Did you miss our last START Webinar?

Do not worry, the "START talks south-west" webinar footage is now online! You can learn about recycling materials in mining environmental liabilities & tetraahedrite as accessory mineral in mineral deposits.

Link: youtube.com/watch?v=9PSTL...

You are welcome to follow our social media account to keep informed!

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Figure 7: The updated Multimedia page.

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Laboratorio Nacional de Energia e Geologia I.P. (PT) – Coordinator	https://www.lneg.pt/
3 Drivers – Engenharia, Inovação E Ambiente Lda (PT)	https://www.3drivers.pt/
Asociacion De Servicios De Geologia Y Minería Iberoamericanos (ES)	https://asgmi.org/
Bundesanstalt Für Geowissenschaften Und Rohstoffe (DE)	https://www.bgr.bund.de/
European Powder Metallurgy Association AISBL (BE)	https://www.epma.com/
GeniCore Sp. Z. o.o. (PL)	https://genicore.eu/
Geo Unterweissacher GmbH (AT)	https://www.geo-unterweissacher.at/
Geosphere Austria (AT)	https://www.geologie.ac.at/
La Palma Research Centre SL (ES)	https://www.lapalmacentre.eu/
MBN Nanomaterialia Spa (IT)	https://www.mbn.it/
RGS Development BV (NL)	https://www.rgsdevelopment.nl/
Statny Geologicky Ustav Dionyza Stura (SK)	https://www.geology.sk/
Sintef AS (NO)	https://www.sintef.no/
TEGnology ApS (DK)	https://www.tegtechnology.dk/
Agencia Estatal Consejo Superior De Investigaciones Científicas (ES)	https://www.csic.es/

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Figure 8: The updated Consortium page.

5.3.1 *EPMA newsletters*

In the weekly newsletter, EPMA is also sending regularly to more than 1600 member contacts the project website link, and in the issue sent out on 23rd May 2023 also a link to download the START newsletter issue #2 from the website (Figure 9). In addition to that, in all quarterly newsletters, distributed to the same number of recipients, EPMA continued to inform its members about the progress in START's activities (as an example, Figure 10 shows the text included in EPMA's quarterly newsletter #127, distributed in March 2023), including the link to download the START Newsletter (for issue #2, this will happen in July 2023).

[View in browser](#)

Weekly News

**EURO
PM2023**
CONGRESS & EXHIBITION
1-4 October 2023, Lisbon Congress Centre

 @Euro_PM2023
www.europm2023.com

EPMA News

Replay our Free HM Webinar

Watch our recent HM Webinar on the 100 year development of Hard Materials.

[Read More >](#)

Registration for Young Engineers 2023 Now Open

Register to take part in the event at Euro PM2023 ahead of the 1 July Deadline

[Read More >](#)

Industry News

ASL Course On Atomization For Metal Powders

On 28th and 29th September Atomising Systems will hold the 15th presentation of the intensive two-day course of Atomization of Metals in Manchester, UK.

[Read More >](#)

Study offers insight into vibration-assisted drilling of AM parts

IFT at TU Wien, and research company Fotec have confirmed through joint investigation that vibration-assisted drilling can be successfully applied to AM components.

[Read More >](#)

New mixer for small volumes

Retsch has introduced a new mixer mill which it says can be used for dry, wet and cryogenic grinding of small sample volumes.

[Read More >](#)

START Project Newsletter Issue #2

The START newsletter is back, with plenty new information about our project and the issues we care about!

[Read More >](#)

EPMA Projects

START Project

[Read More >](#)

ADDress Project

[Read More >](#)

Upcoming Events

MIM Seminar 2023
Taking place this week!

[Read More >](#)

Summer School
Fully Reserved

[Read More >](#)

Euro PM2023
Registration Now Open

[Read More >](#)

EPMA
1 avenue du General de Gaulle, 60500, Chantilly

This email was sent to ac@epma.com
You've received this email because you've subscribed to our newsletter.

[Unsubscribe](#)

Sent with

Figure 9: Content of the EPMA weekly newsletter of 23rd May 2023, with the link to the post on the START website concerning the newsletter and the usual link to the project website.

European Projects

European Project (Continued)

START, a new Horizon Europe project in EPMA's portfolio

The Horizon Europe project START ("Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling"), dealing with thermoelectric materials made from mine waste minerals and to be used in waste heat recovery devices, is coming close to its first year of activity.

EPMA is responsible for the Dissemination and Communication activities, and in that role it leads the efforts to raise awareness about the topics of green energy, energy efficiency, mindful use of resources, etc. As an example, the project's newsletter, whose first edition was published on the project website and social media at the end of November 2022, is named "RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE", demonstrating the intent of communicating not only project news and results, but also contents with a wider scope, in the spirit of the European strive for circularity and energy and resources independence.

Another action is the START webinar series. The eighth event took place on 28th February (the video is available for rewatch here), completely free for participants; the next are planned for 26th April and 1st June. For the moment, the topics are focused on the mining/geology side of the project, as the first tasks are concerning the raw materials.

Another good piece of dissemination is the publication of an article on the magazine Powder Metallurgy Review, spring issue, that covers the general description of the project and an insight of the powder metallurgical aspects of the project: Mechanochemical Synthesis and Pulse Plasma Compaction of the tetrahedrite compositions under study (the article is available here at page 89).

If you are interested in the project, check out its website www.START-HEproject.com, and find out more; you can follow also on Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube, etc. Subscribing to the mailing list on the website will allow to receive directly news about the project, and in particular the newsletter, whose second issue is due in April 2023 and that will be published twice per year.

New Club Project Proposal From Hard Materials Group Of EPMA: Alloyhard

Two Research Centers, CEIT(Spain) and Fraunhofer IKTS(Germany) are proposing a new club project on binder prealloying in hardmetals.

Reducing the cobalt content in WC-Co materials is a challenge for the hardmetal industry due to its increasing use in batteries for electrical vehicles. However, it is not an easy task. So far, alternative hardmetals based on binders including Fe, Ni, Co, Mn, Cu, Cr, Al exhibit different processing issues and poorer mechanical properties. Prealloying may help in avoiding evaporation issues or undesired reactions with presintering and sintering atmospheres.

For more details of the project, read the proposal here.

If you are interested in joining the project as an industrial partner, please contact Kenan Boz from kboz@epma.com

Figure 10: EPMA Newsletter #127, March 2023, page 7.

5.4 SOCIAL MEDIA

Social media are used to engage the audience, bring them to the website, and in general to disseminate and communicate (also to the wider public) about START activities, results and partners.

The project's social media accounts have been already created and reported in deliverable D6.1 ("Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools"), submitted on 29th July 2022. The social media activated are:

- Twitter (partner responsible: LPRC): https://twitter.com/START_HEproject
- LinkedIn (EPMA): <https://www.linkedin.com/company/86266991/>
- YouTube (EPMA): <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCHVjEhpVz9uaEgzlCj2InPA>
- Twitch (LPRC): https://www.twitch.tv/start_he_project
- SlideShare (ASGMI): <https://es.slideshare.net/StartProject/>

In addition to these, an account on the Zenodo service², the Open Data service created by CERN within the OpenAIRE project in 2013, that also offers the creation of a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) number, has been created (see for instance the document [Sustainable energy harvesting systems](#)

² <https://zenodo.org/>

[based on innovative mine waste recycling | Zenodo](#)) by LNEG and will be used, in parallel with SlideShare, to get open access to the START documents (see chapter 6.4).

The use of Zenodo helps us assuring that the rule for OpenAccess publication is fulfilled, together with the publication on our website and social media.

5.4.1 Activity on Twitter

During this period, START Twitter posts had two main goals:

1. sharing information with the community on the project's goals, objectives, and concept, as well as on the relevant communication activities such as presentations at conferences, the START video and online materials and,
2. sharing how the START project contributes to the main topics of interest, e.g., thermoelectrics, reuse of mining waste, waste heat energy, green energy and sustainability.

During M07-M12 a total of 37 posts were made, spanning from 01/12/2022 to 15/05/2023, and contributing to the following statistics:

- 1) Total number of Followers: 65
- 2) Number of views/Impressions during the period: 10356
- 3) Total number of Audience (counted as Engagements + Detail Expands + New followers + Profile visits + Link clicks + Likes + Retweets): 632

Despite the relatively low number of followers, the Twitter posts were seen more than 10000 times. Figure 11 shows the "homepage" of the START Twitter account. See also paragraph 5.8.1.2 for relevant KPIs.

Figure 11: The START Twitter profile (status on 15/05/2023).

5.4.2 Activity on LinkedIn

The activity on LinkedIn went along two main lines:

- Achieving a larger audience for the START page. This was done mainly by EPMA, using the network available to them. At the date of writing D6.3 (29 November 2022), the page followers were 142, on 6th May 2023 the number increased to 312 (Figure 12).
- Posting project news to bring interest and send interested people to the website, if possible, to let them subscribe to the project's mailing list.

Occasionally, some third-party news (e.g., a post on the Critical Raw Materials Act) have been published, in order to create some traffic to the page (a similar approach has been followed on Twitter).

Followers have been growing steadily, growing to more than 300 in May 2023. It is believed that this number will further increase. The objective is to reach 800 followers by the end of the project, and, although difficult to attain, we hope that especially when scientific results will be shown, it will be easier to attract followers.

Figure 12: LinkedIn START followers since project start and until beginning of May 2023 (no “sponsored” followers are present, only “organic”, i.e., normal).

Concerning posts, in the period between 16/11/2022 and 08/05/2023 there were:

- 23 posts on the START page
- 21 posts on LinkedIn groups (“EPMA networking group”, “Sustainability professionals” group, “Thermoelectrics” group, “Thermoelectric matters” group, “Metallurgy and Materials Science” group)

plus, more posts on personal accounts (surely more than 10) by members of the consortium, that have been only partly considered in the evaluation of impact. See also paragraph 5.8.1.1 for relevant KPIs.

5.4.3 Activity on YouTube

On YouTube the activity is lower, as it practically involves the uploading of the videos produced during the project. There was a first introductory video uploaded on 25th October 2022, but in the months covered by this report some more were uploaded. All data reported here have been acquired on 8th May 2023.

5.4.3.1 START introductory video (published on 25th October 2022)

In the first 22 days from publication (25/10/2022-15/11/2022), the START introductory video had 75 visualisations from 48 unique visitors, only one of which subscribed to the channel; a peak of views was after 7 November. To date, visualisations on YouTube have grown to 101, with a constant growth that is still continuing after many months.

Figure 13: Statistics for visualisations of the START introductory video on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication).

The analysis of visualisation behaviour shows that 32.8% of the users actually visualised the video beyond the 30s mark, whereas the average duration of the views is 28 seconds. That would indicate that shorter videos can be more effective, but the content of the video could not be conveyed in a significantly shorter time, in this case.

Figure 14: Statistics for retention of viewers during the START introductory video (YouTube).

5.4.3.2 START Webinar #01 - 2023-28-02 (published on 6th March 2023)

In the first 2 months from publication, the video had 21 visualisations, only one of which subscribed to the channel, and most of them happened within the first week from publication.

Figure 15: Statistics for visualisations of the START Webinar#01 on YouTube (on the x axis, days from publication).

The video is longer than 1 hour, so retention is not very high, only 13.3% of the video is normally watched, for an average duration of 8m29s.

Figure 16: Statistics for retention of viewers during the START Webinar#01 video on YouTube.

5.4.3.3 START - 8th March 2023 - Gracia Olivenza (ASGMI) (published on 8th March 2023)

This was a short video that only got 1 visualisation on YouTube (but much more on other social media). So, no statistics in this case.

5.4.3.4 START - 8th March 2023 - Concepción Fernández Leyva (IGME-CSIC) (published on 8th March 2023)

This was a short video that only got 1 visualisation on YouTube (but much more on other social media). So, no statistics in this case.

5.4.3.5 START Webinar #02 - 2023-04-26 (published on 2nd May 2023)

This video is still collecting visualisation, as it was published only on 2nd May 2023. The visualisations at this point are only 10, so a more detailed statistics may be presented in the next deliverable.

5.4.4 *Activity on Twitch*

Twitch has not been used yet.

5.4.5 *Activity on SlideShare*

As already reported in the previous deliverable D6.3, SlideShare had been used to host six documents prepared that were also uploaded to the website, and some on Zenodo:

Table 2 Presentations and documents uploaded to Slideshare in the first period and their performance.

PRESENTATION/DOCUMENT	LINK	PERFORMANCE
"Green energy harvesting – State of the art"	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/green-energy-harvesting	23 views
"Project START: From WASTE to HIGH-TECH", presentation at EU-Latin America Raw Materials	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/project-start-from-waste-to-hightech	12 views

Convention 2022 (Santiago de Chile, 3-4 November 2022) given by Daniel de Oliveira (LNEG).		
Presentation at World PM 2022 (Lyon, 9-13 October 2022) given by Filipe Neves (LNEG).	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/presentations-at-world-pm2022	8 views
START Factsheet in Portuguese.	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/sistemas-sustentveis-de-captura-de-energia-baseados-uma-abordagem-inovadora-de-reciclagem-de-resduos-de-mina	5 views
START Factsheet in English.	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/sustainable-energy-harvesting-systems-based-on-innovative-mine-waste-recycling	4 views
START Flyer.	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/start-flyer-254343547	6 views

In the last period, only a few more documents were added to SlideShare:

Table 3 Presentations and documents uploaded to Slideshare in the last period and their performance

PRESENTATION/DOCUMENT	LINK	PERFORMANCE
START Newsletter Issue #1	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/startnewsletterissue1pdf	9 views
Starty Explains START – The comics (multilingual)	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/startyexplainsstartpdf	5 views
START Newsletter Issue #2	https://www.slideshare.net/StartProject/startnewsletterissue2pdf	0 views (uploaded 28/05/2023)

The article published on Powder Metallurgy Review will probably be added later: as it is already available in Open Access on the magazine's website, and there was no fee required for its publication, we will discuss with the publisher if we can republish it on SlideShare (and Zenodo) later, after that other magazine issues are already available for readers, in order not to reduce the traffic to the magazine significantly.

5.5 START NEWSLETTER

The project has a Newsletter that is published on its website and social media every 6 months, starting from Issue 1 at M06, November 2022. To give more appeal to the newsletter, the consortium chose a name that is suggesting that the content will not be just related to START but will be strictly connected with the sustainability solutions imagined. The name was decided among the consortium before the first issue was prepared: "RECOVER – REFORM - REUSE". This brings in the ideas of recovering (mine wastes, heat), of transformation (of wastes into raw materials for

thermoelectric devices, of otherwise dispersed heat into electrical energy), and of reusing (materials and energy achieved to obtain better efficiency).

The information conveyed in the various issues of the newsletter will in fact always include:

- General information about START, thermoelectric materials, energy harvesting from waste heat, and linked sustainability topics, including state-of-the-art documents and scientific reviews
- Updates on project activities
- Updates on project events and other dissemination topics, with invitation to join events where START will be featured
- Description of consortium partners (typically 2 per issue)
- All information on the various ways to keep informed about START (links to website, social media, link to the contact and subscription forms, etc.)

With the progress in the project, and the need to stimulate exploitation, the length of the publication will increase.

Being completely public, the information in the Newsletter must be duly checked in order to avoid IPR management issues.

The distribution is partly based on a list of subscribers (and partly on social media and other partners networks). To create this list, the website tool for registration is used, and social media posts attract new subscribers to the website tool.

5.5.1 Newsletter issue #1

Issue #1 was published in November 2022 and was covered in deliverable D6.3. As it had been published at the end of November, the data on downloads and its impact were not available yet, so the analysis was carried out later.

From the website, the newsletter had been downloaded 193 times since 28/11/2022 (data of 6th May 2023). It is likely that some more downloads will happen when subsequent issues are published.

On LinkedIn it was posted as a document on 8th December 2022, after a first post that just linked to the news on the website. It got the following feedback:

- 397 Impressions
- 20 Reactions
- 22.67% Click-through rate
- 0 Comments
- 7 Reposts
- 90 Clicks
- 29.47% Engagement rate [Calculated as (Likes + Comments + Shares + Clicks + Follows)/Impressions]

The number of impressions is significantly higher than the page followers at the date of publication (less than 200), and particularly the Click through rate and the Engagement rate are remarkable, as about 1/3 of viewers reacted actively to it.

On Twitter the Newsletter was shared first on 29th November and again on 6th December, referring to the website post. They got the following feedback:

- 565 + 292 impressions
- 43 + 15 total engagements
 - 13 detail expands
 - 12 + 7 Likes
 - 7 + 4 Retweets
 - 6 Profile Clicks
 - 3 Link Clicks
 - 5 +1 Media engagements
- 7.6% + 5.1% engagement rate

On Zenodo it was uploaded on 29th November 2022 and was viewed 19 times and downloaded 15 times (data of 6th May 2023).

So, in general it seems that the document was well received. In D6.3 we already documented that it had been delivered to more than 500 recipients, that was the KPI foreseen: clearly, downloads are lower (more than 200 anyway) but this may be better for next issues if the readers are retained and new ones will add.

5.5.2 Newsletter issue #2

The Issue 2 of the newsletter was prepared in the months of April/May 2023. Using the template that EPMA already created for Issue #1, text and images were collected from the different partners and were graphically rearranged to generate this issue.

The content of the issue is as follows:

- Editorial
- STARTY – 2: The geology work in START
- START Chronicles: Geology and more
 - News from WorkPackage2 “Selection of mine waste sites; physical minerals separation and concentration”: Tetrahedrites collected in Slovakia have been analysed and successfully concentrated
 - News from WorkPackage3 “Materials modelling and processing”: activity on Mechanochemical Synthesis and Pulse Plasma Compaction of Tetrahedrites
 - START’s Scientific Advisory Board appointed
 - New equipment acquired by LNEG to work on START materials
 - START webinars
 - START and gender balance
 - START on the magazine “Powder Metallurgy Review”
 - START on the magazine “água&ambiente”
 - START on the magazine “Ingenium”
 - STARTY in 12 languages!
 - START dissemination events
- Technical pills
 - Tetrahedrites in the world
 - Powder metallurgy of tetrahedrites

- Meet the Scientific Advisory Board Members
- Consortium tour
 - TEGnology
 - RGS Development
- Contacts

The total size of this issue #2 is 23 pages (Issue #1 had 11 pages). A full version is available in Annex I.

Compared to Issue #1, clearly there is new content in the already existing sections, but also a new section, that where the members of the Scientific Advisory Board will be presented one by one with a short interview, starting in Issue #2 with J. Hollis of EuroGeoSurveys. We believe that this second issue is technically more interesting than the opening issue, and we will try to expand in this direction in next issues.

The newsletter was uploaded to the website on the Documents page (with reference also in the News page) on 22 May 2023 and was uploaded also to Zenodo³ (25th May 2023). It was advertised on Twitter (22 May 2023) and LinkedIn (22 May 2023). The launch of Issue #2 was announced on the EPMA weekly Newsletter for members on 25th May 2023 (Figure 9) and will be announced later to non-members (about 1600 and 400 contacts, respectively). A news item on the EPMA quarterly newsletter will be sent to all EPMA members (about 1600 contacts) in July 2023. The data for downloads will be analysed in the next weeks.

5.6 *START COMICS - STARTY*

As already explained in previous Deliverables, START is making use of a comics character, “Starty, the robot”, that will be employed as much as possible to make communication more appealing also to those categories in the target that are not too scientifically involved in the subject, including the general public. This character will guide the reader or viewer into the START contents.

Starty already was the main character in the introductory video developed in September 2022, and in a first storyboard on the first issue of the START Newsletter “RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE” issued in November 2022 (Figure 17).

³ 10.5281/zenodo.7925963

Figure 17: The first Starty strip, included in the START Newsletter #1, November 2022.

This strip was later translated in 11 more languages, including all languages spoken in the consortium, with the addition of Turkish. A collection of all these strips was titled “Starty explains

START (multilingual edition)” and was launched on Zenodo on 31st March 2023⁴ and on the website on 1st April 2023. Since then, it has been downloaded 37 times (data of 6th May 2023). As an example, we report here the Turkish version (Figure 18).

Figure 18: “Starty explains START” in Turkish.

⁴ 10.5281/zenodo.7746441

In Newsletter Issue #2, Starty's space tripled to 3 pages (see Annex I). We will do a translation effort for this short story as well, but this will happen in the next period.

5.7 VIDEOS

According to what was planned in the proposal, at least 5 videos will be produced during the project:

- 2 short videos (0.5-1 min), one at the start of the project to raise awareness and one at the end to summarise results. The language should be suitable for a wider audience; animations or cartoons could be used to attract non-specialists. One video at M04 (September 2022), one at M48 (May 2026).
- 2 longer videos (but still not too long, max 3 min) during the project, focusing on project topics and activities. The target should be more to groups 2-3, i.e., scientists, engineers, and entrepreneurs. Both videos are due at M48 (May 2026)
- 1 detailed video (about 5 min) at mid project (M24, May 2024), highlighting the results of the first part of the project.

Other videos could be produced, like:

- Interviews with key partners, describing the project or specific topics
- Recording of presentations given in events
- Short ads for specific events or for the "serious game"

EPMA will be taking care of producing the videos but will ask all relevant partners to help by delivering videos, images, and text. The videos will be hosted on YouTube and/or Twitch, will be embedded in the START website, and posted on other social media like LinkedIn and Twitter.

The KPIs decided for these tools are basically views. A minimum of 100 views per video is the base KPI, and an overall average above 200 views/video is an additional KPI. Clearly, the different social media analysis tools allow collecting even further information about the audience.

5.7.1 START introductory video

As originally planned, a short introductory video for the project has been created in September 2022. It was decided to use Starty, our robot testimonial, to give the introductory info about START in the form of balloons in every slide. The video was then uploaded to the START YouTube page (<https://youtu.be/-x8XGUrVAfs>), embedded in the START website, on the home page and in the Multimedia page, and posted to LinkedIn and Twitter. The video has already been used in some events: for instance, World PM2022 and Raw Materials Week 2022.

The views are being tracked, in order to prove that the KPIs established are achieved.

This is the situation on 8th May 2023:

- YouTube (published on 25th October 2022):
 - views: 101
 - Average duration of viewing: 0m28s
 - Average duration of viewing, %: 32.8%
- LinkedIn (published on 26th October 2022):

- 791 video views⁵
- 509 Impressions⁶
- 19 Reactions
- 3.14% Click-through rate
- 10 Reposts
- 16 Clicks
- 8.84% Engagement Rate⁷
- Twitter (published on 21st November 2022):
 - 60 impressions
 - 4 total engagements
 - 3 likes
 - 1 Retweet
 - 6.7% engagement rate

As visible, the number of views largely exceeds the minimum set, and is also way above the average requested of 200.

5.7.2 *Second START video*

A second START video will be produced in the next months. It will be a somewhat longer video, dedicated mainly to the geology side of the activity, that was the core of the activities in this first year of the project. The partners are collecting pictures and short clips that may be used for that.

5.7.3 *Other videos*

5.7.3.1 *Presentation of START at the Science Week 2022, Madrid*

This video was not produced by the project, but recorded by the event organisers, and made available. It was linked to the actual YouTube page on our website. There, 170 views are reported at the moment of writing this deliverable, but no further detail is available. On LinkedIn, it was “reposted” from a post of the Colegio Oficial de Geólogos that had organised the event, so no detail on the number of visualisations is available either. As the video is in Spanish, the impact is clearly focused in the Spanish-speaking countries.

5.7.3.2 *8th March videos*

These videos were self-recorded by the two female members of the START team who represented all the females in the consortium on the occasion of the International Women Day. They were posted embedded in the news post in the website’s News page, that got 12 visualisations, whilst direct hits on YouTube are 3 per video. On the other hand, the posts on the LinkedIn page (148 and 151 video views each) had a much better result. On Twitter a post was shared with information

⁵ Video views Total: Views with 3 or more seconds of playback while the video is at least 50% on screen.

⁶ Impressions: Views when the update is at least 50% on screen, or when it is clicked, whichever comes first.

⁷ Engagement rate: Calculated as (Likes+Comments+Shares+Clicks+Follows)/Impressions

linking to the news item on the START webinar, getting 96 impressions and 13 total engagements, achieving an engagement rate of 13.5%.

5.7.3.3 Webinar #01

This is the footage of the first START webinar, held on 28th February 2023, trimmed and perfected with entry and exit titles. It is 1 h 3 m long. On YouTube, the number of views is at the moment 26; on LinkedIn and Twitter it was not posted as a video, rather as a link to the News page of the website where the video is embedded (based on the YouTube hosting). We plan to post the video on LinkedIn later, in a time with less activity, and more views will be collected.

5.7.3.4 Webinar #02

This is the footage of the second START webinar, held on 26th April 2023, trimmed and perfected with entry and exit titles. It is 1 h 17 m long. On YouTube, the number of views is at the moment 11; on LinkedIn it was not posted as a video, rather as a link to the News page of the website where the video is embedded (based on the YouTube hosting). In this case as well, we plan to post the video on LinkedIn and Twitter later, in a time with less activity, and more views will be collected.

5.8 CONTINUOUS EVALUATION OF D&C PERFORMANCE

5.8.1 KPIs

KPIs are “a quantifiable measure of performance over time for a specific objective”. Although they are not the same as metrics, in the case of measuring the performance of a website or a social media that is normal.

To assess the dissemination, START will collect metrics from the website, and the social media, and will compare some selected KPIs to chosen reference values that the project expects to meet of the years. A list of the KPIs imagined, with their reference values, is given in Table 4.

Table 4: KPIs considered for D&C activities.

Tool	KPI	Reference value
Project website	Visitors	Year 1: 2000 Year 4: 4000
Twitter	Followers	Year 1: 1000 End: 2500
LinkedIn	Followers	End:800
Videos	Views	More than 100/video Average 200
Newsletters	Addressees	More than 500/issue
Webinars/ seminars/ workshop	Audience	100
Serious online game	Visitors	300
Other publications	Reach	More than 400000

According to previous project experiences, as already shown in deliverable D6.1 (“Creation of the project website, graphical identity and other online tools”), an Excel file, named Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination (MTOD) is used to collect the data of dissemination performance on social media, in order to quantify the audience reached and the interest raised.

This is located on the START SharePoint (its address is [START/Work Packages/WP6 - Dissemination and communication/START Monitoring Tool for Online Dissemination.xlsx⁸](#)) and contains all the details collected from the different social media posts and contents, and from the website. A view of the present status of the file is visible in the screenshot of Figure 19.

The file allows to calculate total audience and views of the actions, and the ratio between views and audience for each action. In this way, during the project course, priorities about the social media could be given.

The data from this file is used to update the Funding & Tender website page on Dissemination (see 5.8.3).

At present, about 150 lines are included in the file; the sum of all audience data is close to 500k and the sum of views is more than 35000.

Views have had highs of about 1850 (on Twitter) and 1400 (on LinkedIn), with a median of about 145 and an average of about 235.

We believe that, considering the initial phase and the fact that this is a new subject for many of the contacts, the performance can be considered satisfactory: views have a median that is close to the average number of followers in the period, so most of them actually visualise our content.

⁸ Note: this is a private address, not accessible from outside the Consortium.

What	When	Who	Where	Where2	Views	V_Data%	V/A	Audience	Notes	End date
High					1845			9700.0%	305705	
Low					3			0.0%	3	
Median					146			68.1%	260	
Average					235			66.0%	3479	
Total					83315			476460		
Post on KickOff Meeting	2022-06-27	EPMA	LinkedIn	EPMA Page	1045	2022-10-18	21.3%	4900	Reactions: 16; clicks: 30	2022-07-27
Post on KickOff Meeting	2022-06-27	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	445	2022-10-18	31.8%	1400	Reactions: 5	2022-07-27
Post on KickOff Meeting	2022-06-27	R. Ravez (EPMA)	Website	START website	3	2023-05-08				2022-09-25
Post on the kick-off Meeting	2022-07-07	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	1136	2022-11-07	1646.4%	69	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-08-06
Green Energy Harvesting	2022-07-16	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	136	2022-11-07	1022.4%	14	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-12-23
Post on START methodology and goals	2022-07-28	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	1565	2022-11-07	1558.6%	87	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-08-27
Post on START concept - link to webpage	2022-08-18	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	35	2022-11-07	1750.0%	2	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-09-17
Post on KickOff Meeting	2022-08-09	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	152	2022-10-18	776.5%	17	Reactions: 9; clicks: 3; reposts: 5	2022-09-08
Post on START Factsheet	2022-08-26	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	402	2022-11-07	708.5%	57	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-10-26
Post on World PM2022	2022-10-04	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	98	2022-11-04	753.8%	11	Reactions: 2; clicks: 2; reposts: 3	2022-11-03
Post on World PM2022	2022-10-04	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	150	2022-11-04	10.0%	1500	Reactions: 0; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-11-03
Post on World PM2022	2022-10-05	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	143	2022-11-04	1022.4%	14	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-11-04
Post on World PM2022 End	2022-10-13	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	136	2022-11-14	1046.2%	13	Reactions: 5; clicks: 20; reposts: 1	2022-11-12
Post on World PM2022 End	2022-10-13	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	401	2022-11-14	26.7%	1500	Reactions: 11; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-11-12
Post on World PM2022 End	2022-10-13	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	141	2022-11-14	698.5%	15	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-11-12
Post on START objectives	2022-10-21	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	215	2023-05-15	1075.0%	20	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-11-20
Introductory video	2022-10-25	EPMA	YouTube	START channel	97	2023-03-14	9700.0%	0	Like/Disklike: -/	2022-01-23
Post on introductory video	2022-10-26	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	739	2022-12-07	4926.7%	15	Reactions: 19; clicks: 14; reposts: 10	2022-11-25
Post on introductory video	2022-10-26	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	309	2023-05-08		1500	Reactions: 4; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-11-25
World PM2022 news post	2022-10-27	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	169	2023-05-15	603.6%	28	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-11-26
Post on introductory video	2022-10-27	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	334	2022-12-07	2220.0%	16	Reactions: 14; clicks: 13; reposts: 3	2022-11-26
Post on World PM2022 Website news post	2022-10-27	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	475	2022-12-07	31.7%	1500	Reactions: 9; clicks: 0; reposts: 0; comment: 2	2022-11-26
Post on World PM2022 Website news post	2022-11-02	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	140	2022-12-07	386.7%	75	Reactions: 7; clicks: 3; reposts: 6	2022-12-02
Post on EU-LaSam Convention	2022-11-02	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	111	2022-12-07	20.7%	1000	Reactions: 4; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-12-02
Post on EU-LaSam Convention	2022-11-02	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	EPMA Networking group	170	2022-12-07	5.0%	3414	Reactions: 1; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-12-02
Post on EU-LaSam Convention	2022-11-02	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	"Sustainability Professionals" group	41	2022-12-07	0.0%	309705	Reactions: 0; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-12-02
Post on EU-LaSam Convention	2022-11-03	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	149	2022-12-12	931.3%	16	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-12-03
Post on EU-LaSam Convention/photos live	2022-11-03	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	296	2022-12-07	352.4%	84	Reactions: 19; clicks: 49; reposts: 7	2022-12-03
Post on EU-LaSam Convention/photos live	2022-11-03	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	300	2022-12-07	20.0%	2500	Reactions: 3; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-12-03
Post on EU-LaSam Convention/photos live	2022-11-04	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	EPMA Networking group	315	2022-12-07	9.2%	3414	Reactions: 1; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-12-04
Post on EU-LaSam Convention	2022-11-07	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	712	2022-12-08	2966.7%	24	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-12-07
Post on Science Week Madrid 22 / Launch	2022-11-08	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	433	2023-01-10	424.5%	102	Reactions: 25; clicks: 11; reposts: 7	2022-12-08
Post on Science Week Madrid 22 / Launch	2022-11-08	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	107	2023-01-10	26.1%	1507	Reactions: 2; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-12-08
Post on Science Week Madrid 22 / Launch	2022-11-08	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	107	2022-12-12	764.3%	14	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-12-08
Post on Science Week Madrid 22 / Video	2022-11-14	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	164	2023-01-10	113.9%	144	Reactions: 7; clicks: 2; reposts: 0	2022-12-14
Post on Science Week Madrid 22 / Video	2022-11-14	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	367	2023-01-10	24.1%	1520	Reactions: 1; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-12-14
Post on Science Week Madrid 22 / Video	2022-11-15	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	EPMA Networking group	123	2023-01-10	3.6%	3433	Reactions: 0; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-12-15
Post on introductory video	2022-11-15	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	"Thermoelectrics" group	70	2023-01-10	11.1%	631	Reactions: 2; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-12-15
Post on Enter Bioenergies Via of ICMR present	2022-11-15	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	345	2023-05-15		1	Reactions: 0; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-12-15
Post on START at the Raw Materials Week	2022-11-21	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	43	2023-05-15		4	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-12-21
Post on START LinkedIn page (follow)	2022-11-23	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	648	2023-01-10	42.4%	1530	Reactions: 16; clicks: 0; reposts: 2	2022-12-23
Post on START LinkedIn page (follow)	2022-11-23	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	EPMA Networking group	131	2023-01-10	6.7%	3435	Reactions: 5; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-12-23
Post on START Website on START NL#1	2022-11-29	EPMA	Website	START website	120	2023-05-08				2023-02-27
Post on EPMA Website on START NL#1	2022-11-29	EPMA	Website	EPMA website	52	2022-12-07			Clicks: 212	2023-02-27
Item on EPMA Weekly Newsletter for Member	2022-11-29	EPMA	E-Mail (Mailchimp)	EPMA members list	641	2022-12-07	40.4%	1585	Clicks: 212	2022-12-06
Post on START NL#1	2022-11-29	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	145	2023-01-10	784.8%	145	Reactions: 14; clicks: 28; reposts: 7	2022-12-29
Post on START NL#1	2022-11-29	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	139	2023-01-10	9.0%	1538	Reactions: 1; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-12-29
Post on START NL#1	2022-11-29	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	EPMA Networking group	191	2023-01-10	5.6%	3435	Reactions: 2; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-12-29
Post on START NL#1	2022-11-29	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	"Thermoelectrics" group	84	2023-01-10	13.3%	1000	Reactions: 1; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2022-12-29
Post on START NL#1	2022-11-29	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	170	2023-05-15	653.8%	26	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-12-29
Post to share START Media Channels links	2022-12-01	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	61	2023-05-15	610.0%	10	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-12-31
Post on START NL#1	2022-12-05	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	164	2023-05-15	1760.0%	10	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2022-12-31
Item on EPMA Weekly Newsletter for Member	2022-12-02	EPMA	E-Mail (Mailchimp)	EPMA nonmembers list	115	2023-05-15	35.5%	324	Clicks: 58	2022-12-09
Post with START NL#1	2022-12-08	EPMA	LinkedIn	START Page	310	2023-01-10	191.4%	162	Reactions: 20; clicks: 88; reposts: 7	2023-01-07
Post with START NL#1	2022-12-08	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	283	2023-01-10	28.4%	1538	Reactions: 3; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2023-01-07
Post on World PM2022 Congress & Exhib	2022-12-08	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	4	2023-05-15	875.0%	4	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2023-01-07
Post about the START Consortium	2022-12-14	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	265	2023-05-15	1204.5%	22	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2023-01-14
Post on a WFS meeting	2022-12-15	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	136	2023-05-15	1050.0%	32	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2023-01-14
Post to link to state of the art waste energy	2022-12-19	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	147	2023-05-15	1239.0%	14	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2023-01-14
Post on START on the CORDIS page	2023-01-03	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	604	2023-02-13	2416.0%	25	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2023-02-02
Post on SAB appointment	2023-01-12	EPMA	Website	START Website	36	2023-02-03				2023-04-12
Post on SAB appointment	2023-01-12	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	602	2023-01-13	311.9%	193	Reactions: 18; clicks: 72; reposts: 3	2023-02-11
Post on SAB appointment	2023-01-12	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	250	2023-03-14	16.2%	1546	Reactions: 2; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2023-02-11
Post on SAB appointment	2023-01-12	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	19	2023-02-13	1900.0%	1	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2023-02-11
Post on SAB appointment	2023-01-12	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	209	2023-05-15	983.3%	10	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2023-02-11
Post on SAB appointment	2023-01-12	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	89	2023-05-15	890.0%	10	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2023-05-05
Post on Webinar Series	2023-02-07	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	Website	START Website	75	2023-05-15				2023-05-08
Post on Webinar01	2023-02-07	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	START Page	3428	2023-02-07	143.5%	239	Reactions: 17; clicks: 16; reposts: 11	2023-03-09
Post on Webinar01	2023-02-07	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	220	2023-03-14	14.1%	1559	Reactions: 1; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2023-03-09
Post on Webinar01	2023-02-07	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	"Thermoelectrics" group	63	2023-03-14	9.9%	634	Reactions: 2; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2023-03-09
Post on Webinar01	2023-02-07	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	EPMA Networking group	248	2023-03-14	6.8%	3629	Reactions: 1; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2023-03-09
Post on Webinar01	2023-02-07	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	"Thermoelectric matters" group	180	2023-03-15	125.0%	17	Reactions: 0; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2023-03-09
Post on Webinar01	2023-02-07	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	58	2023-05-15	20.0%	290	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2023-03-09
Post on Webinar01	2023-02-14	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	146	2023-05-15	1622.2%	9	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2023-03-16
Post on Webinar01 Speaker 1	2023-02-14	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	111	2023-05-15	111.2%	29	Reactions: 15; clicks: 6; reposts: 4	2023-03-16
Post on Webinar01 Speaker 1	2023-02-14	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	EPMA Networking group	142	2023-05-08	3.9%	3629	Reactions: 0; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2023-03-16
Post on Thermoelectrics conference	2023-02-16	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	127	2023-05-15	635.0%	20	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2023-03-18
Post on Webinar01 Speaker 2	2023-02-16	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	129	2023-05-15	124.2%	265	Reactions: 13; clicks: 4; reposts: 3	2023-03-18
Post on Webinar01 Speaker 2	2023-02-16	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	100	2023-05-08	6.4%	1559	Reactions: 0; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2023-03-18
Post on Webinar01 Speaker 2	2023-02-14	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	EPMA Networking group	165	2023-05-08	4.3%	3629	Reactions: 2; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2023-03-16
Post on Webinar01	2023-02-14	LRPC	Twitter	START Page	25	2023-05-15	2348.0%	1	Audience + Engagements + Detail Expand	2023-03-16
Post on Webinar01 Registration -7	2023-02-21	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	START Page	293	2023-05-08	118.1%	248	Reactions: 6; clicks: 13; reposts: 8	2023-03-23
Post on Webinar01 Registration -7	2023-02-21	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	Own account	55	2023-05-08	3.3%	1559	Reactions: 0; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2023-03-23
Post on Webinar01 Registration -7	2023-02-21	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	EPMA Networking group	176	2023-05-08	4.8%	3629	Reactions: 1; clicks: 0; reposts: 0	2023-03-23
Reflect on Webinar01 Speaker 1	2023-02-21	B. Vicenzi (EPMA)	LinkedIn	START Page	118	2023-05-1				

5.8.1.1 LinkedIn

For LinkedIn, the number of followers is now above 300 (see also chapter 5.4.2), that is still below the target of 800 followers at the end of the project, but more than double compared to the data in November 2022 reported in D6.3. Followers mainly grow by invitations, and invitations to follow are limited to 100/month per LinkedIn settings. The distance is not felt critical yet. A plot of the number of new followers (see Figure 12) shows that there was a larger addition around the time of the first newsletter published, so we will evaluate the effect of the second newsletter now. Also, page views (Figure 20) had a peak at that time, and then lower numbers. Impressions (Figure 21) show a second peak around end of February 2023, presumably due to the first webinar.

Figure 20: LinkedIn visitor metrics.

Figure 21: LinkedIn impressions metrics.

5.8.1.2 Twitter

For Twitter the number of actual followers (currently at 65) is rather low, compared to the planned target for Year 1. This can be explained by the lack of project news and activities, which are planned to expand from year 2 onwards, and also by the recent turmoil regarding Twitter itself as a platform. The number of audiences reached – counting the number of views/impressions, Likes, Retweets, Engagements, Detail Expands, New followers and Profile visits – is, however, interesting (more than 10000 between December 2022 and May 2023): this number corresponds to real engagement with the project posts, so it can be considered as a more reliable parameter for KPIs assessment. Clearly, we will still try to increase the number of followers, but propose to modify the actual KPI to achieve for Twitter from “followers” to “views and impressions”.

The figure below shows the increase of the START Twitter activity between 23rd October and 23rd November 2022, boosted by the many events where START was presented to different stakeholders.

Figure 22: Top: Twitter impressions and Tweets from 01/12/22 to 28/02/2023. Bottom: Twitter impressions and Tweets from 01/03/23 to 12/05/2023.

5.8.1.3 Videos

For the videos “planned”, we have the following:

- Introductory video: YouTube led to 101 views by the date of writing this report, including those generated by the views on the website, posts on LinkedIn (about 800) and Twitter (about 60) amount to about 860 views. So, the KPI of at least 100 views, and even the average expected of 200 views, are exceeded by far.

For the originally (in the proposal) “unplanned videos”, we have collected about 40 visualisations on YouTube and many more on LinkedIn, about 300 (from the International Women Day videos). For the webinar footage videos we did not collect views on social media apart from YouTube, as the actual videos have not been posted there yet, only links to the website and YouTube.

5.8.1.4 Project website

Concerning the project website, we remind here that the analysis is limited to the data after 17th October 2022 because of an erroneous setting of Google Analytics: all data before 17th October have been lost. For the following periods, these data have been collected:

- Audience (users, new users, numbers of sessions per user, pageviews, pages/session)
- Acquisition
- Behaviour (visited pages)

We compare in the following pages the data for 1 month (mid-October to mid-November 2022, Period 1) to those in the following months (mid-November 2022 to mid-May 2023, Period 2). Clearly, the ratio 1:6 of actual days covered must be considered.

Figure 23 shows the Audience data for Period 1, and Figure 25 the data for Period 2. In both periods, as visible in Figure 25, there was one peak, roughly of the same amount, about 400 users, that are not likely due to normal traffic (bots?), as they happened on a day when some post on social media was published, but these peaks are mostly coming from direct sources, although from different countries, not from social media.

Audience				
Period:	17/10/2022	16/11/2022	Days:	31
Audience	Users	New users	Sessions	Pages/session
Total/average	621	621	675	1.45
New visitors	621	621	621	1.36
Returning visitors	17	0	54	2.52
Sessions				
Sessions/user	1.09			
Page views	980			1.45
Device				
Desktop	591			1.45
Mobile	30			1.52

Figure 23: Google Analytics data for the period 17/10/2022-16/11/2022: Audience.

Audience				
Period:	17/11/2022	09/05/2023	Days:	174
Audience	Users	New users	Sessions	Pages/session
Total/average	1788	1767	2111	1.63
New visitors	1767	1767	1767	1.50
Returning visitors	132	0	344	2.31
Sessions				
Sessions/user	1.18			
Page views	3437			1.63
Device				
Desktop	1542			1.65
Mobile	242			1.49
Tablet	4			1.75

Figure 24: Google Analytics data for the period 17/11/2022-10/05/2023: Audience.

Figure 25: Google Analytics data for the period 17/10/2022-10/05/2023: Users per day. The two probably spurious peaks are clearly visible.

Comparing the two tables, of course the values are higher for Period 2, but the intensity seems to be lower. “Depurating” the data with 400 users less in both periods (clearly an estimate), the intensity becomes similar: e.g., 221 users in Period 1 (7.1 per day) and 1388 in Period 2 (8.0 per day), and even a little higher for Period 2, as hoped.

The table with the total for all the available days is shown in Figure 26. Considering the days effectively analysed, and projecting the data to 365 days, about 4250 users are calculated. Even reducing the users by about 800, the expected yearly figure would be about 2850.

Page views per year were more than 4400, so 7900 per year; considering that the 2 peaks were created by users that visited only 1 page, so each spurious user generated only one page view, a recalculation would bring to about 6500 page views per year.

In the comparison, it is also interesting to note that the average number of pages per session is slightly increasing in Period 2, that is a good sign.

Audience				
Period:	17/10/2022	09/05/2023	Days:	205
Audience	Users	New users	Sessions	Pages/session
Total/365 days	4264.3	4264.3	4987.1	
Total/average	2395	2395	2801	1.58
New visitors	2395	2395	2395	1.46
Returning visitors	144	0	406	2.31
Sessions				
Sessions/user	1.18			
Page views	4435			1.58
Page views/365 days	7896.5			
Device				
Desktop	2117			1.59
Mobile	274			1.49
Tablet	4			1.75

Figure 26: Google Analytics data for the period 17/10/2022-10/05/2023: Audience.

Actually, even removing the dubious peaks, and even without estimating the contribution of the about 3 months missing in the data (mid-July to mid-October), **the total page views (about 3600) are way above the requested KPI of 2000 views in the first year, and probably already higher, when projected on a yearly basis, than the KPI for the end-of-project regime (4000 views).**

Concerning the ways to arrive to the website, Figure 27 shows that table for period 1, Figure 28 that for Period 2, and Figure 29 the total. Most of entries happen via direct URL selection in the browser, whereas traffic from social media, searches and referral sites is rather limited, but the sources other than direct are increasing and this would be even more important removing about 800 hits from the spurious peaks, that were direct sources.

Acquisition channels				
Period:	17/10/2022	16/11/2022	Days:	31
Channel	Users	New users	Sessions	Pages/session
Total/average	621	621	675	1.45
Direct	592	592	633	1.43
Social	17	17	20	1.70
Organic search	10	9	17	1.82
Referral	4	3	5	1.60

Figure 27: Google Analytics data for the period 17/10/2022-16/11/2022: Acquisition channels.

Acquisition channels				
Period:	17/11/2022	09/05/2023	Days:	174
Channel	Users	New users	Sessions	Pages/session
Total/average	1788	1767	2111	1.63
Direct	1373	1359	1505	1.46
Social	139	121	254	2.12
Organic search	253	248	292	2.03
Referral	47	39	60	1.80

Figure 28: Google Analytics data for the period 17/11/2022-10/05/2023: Acquisition channels.

Acquisition channels				
Period:	17/10/2022	09/05/2023	Days:	205
Channel	Users	New users	Sessions	Pages/session
Total/365 days	4264.3	4264.3	4987.1	
Total/average	2395	2395	2801	1.58
Direct	1954	1954	2142	1.45
Social	158	140	280	2.07
Organic search	266	259	314	2.01
Referral	50	42	65	1.78

Figure 29: Google Analytics data for the period 17/10/2022-10/05/2023: Acquisition channels.

In Period 1, the most visited page was the homepage, followed by the “Contact” page (Figure 30). It was expected that the “Documents” and the “News” pages will have more hits with the publication of the already mentioned material. Actually, in Period 2 (Figure 31) all other pages grew and passed: “Project”, “Document”, “Consortium” and “News” all are before “Contact”, only “Multimedia” has a lower ranking, topped also by the news item about the first issue of the Newsletter. If we consider that the users in the spurious peaks mostly accessed the homepage, the share of the other pages becomes even more important.

Performance of pages				
Period:	17/10/2022	16/11/2022	Days:	31
Page	Page views	Unique views	Time on page (s)	Arrivals
<i>Total/average</i>	980	877	87.6	675
/	653	611	55.1	598
/contact/	62	52	150.1	34
/the-project/	60	47	65.9	10
/documents/	56	49	233.8	6
/consortium/	55	36	68.7	3
/news/	42	35	153.9	4
/multimedia/	23	19	8.3	0
/news-start-wpm2022/	20	19	44.3	13
/&data=05 01 filipe.nev	2	2	401.0	0
/&data=05 01 filipe.nev	1	1	0.0	1

Figure 30: Google Analytics data for the period 17/10/2022-16/11/2022: Performance of pages.

Performance of pages				
Period:	17/11/2022	09/05/2023	Days:	174
Page	Page views	Unique views	Time on page (s)	Arrivals
<i>Total/average</i>	3437	3022	75.3	2111
/	1817	1646	66.9	1579
/the-project/	279	223	52.3	24
/documents/	270	215	115.2	51
/consortium/	171	141	73.8	24
/news/	160	131	35.6	5
/contact/	137	117	79.6	50
/recover-reform-reuse-is	120	110	99.5	91
/multimedia/	102	93	54.4	17
/start-on-powder-metall	89	82	251.1	75
/start-free-webinar-serie	75	71	89.6	59
/start-looks-southwest-t	59	49	321.8	37
/starty-comics-starty-exp	36	31	79.8	27
/the-project-scientific-ad	36	32	68.4	18
/more-than-60-participa	28	25	63.1	23
/*	16	16	0.2	9
/1350-2/	12	11	467.3	7
/news-start-wpm2022/	8	8	30.0	3
/the-footage-of-the-seco	4	4	72.0	2

Figure 31: Google Analytics data for the period 17/11/2022-10/05/2023: Performance of pages.

Performance of pages				
Period:	17/10/2022	09/05/2023	Days:	205
Page	Page views	Unique views	Time on page (s)	Arrivals
Total/365 days	7896.5	6974.2		4987.1
Total/average	4435	3917	77.5	2801
/	2475	2262	64.3	2182
/the-project/	340	271	54.5	34
/documents/	326	252	105.9	54
/consortium/	227	190	108.0	30
/contact/	199	169	100.0	84
/news/	184	151	32.0	5
/multimedia/	144	128	82.8	21
/recover-reform-reuse-is	121	111	99.5	92
/start-on-powder-metall	89	82	251.1	75
/start-free-webinar-serie	75	71	89.6	59
/start-looks-southwest-t	59	49	321.8	37
/starty-comics-starty-exp	36	31	79.8	27
/the-project-scientific-ad	36	32	68.4	18
/more-than-60-participa	28	25	63.1	23
/news-start-wpm2022/	28	27	40.8	16
/*	16	16	0.2	9
/1350-2/	12	11	467.3	7
/join-the-third-webinar-c	9	9	0.0	9
/the-footage-of-the-seco	4	4	72.0	2

Figure 32: Google Analytics data for the period 17/10/2022-10/05/2023: Performance of pages.

Globally, we can consider the website performance as rather satisfactory, and the hope is that with the progress in the project, and more meaningful scientific content being published, the performance may become even better.

5.8.1.5 *Newsletter*

Concerning the newsletter, the distribution through the START mailing list now comprises about 170 names, more than double compared to the distribution list for Issue #1 (80). Nevertheless, EPMA has sent the link to download the Newsletter to about 1600 EPMA member contacts via its weekly E-Mail Newsletter on 25th May, and a new mailing will be done in early June to a list of about 400 non-members. Since the Newsletter was ready only at the end of May 2023, data for downloads or actual views of this issue are not available yet and will be reported in the next deliverable of this series (D6.6). Anyway, especially via the EPMA distribution, the target of 500 has been potentially exceeded by far; clearly it will have to be correlated with the actual downloads recorded.

5.8.2 WP6 meetings

To keep track of the activities and their performance, and steer them during the project, the WP6 main partners are called to meet, normally online but in-person meetings are also possible. These include:

- the WP6 leader (EPMA)
- the other WP6 task leader (ASGMI)
- the other partner responsible for social media accounts (LPRC)
- the coordinator (LNEG)
- the leaders of WPs, i.e., the components of the ExCom
- specific partners that will be invited if their participation will be useful in the discussion, for instance if their activity is required in the following months.

Anyway, during this semester, only smaller meetings were organised for specific discussions, like the detailed organisation of a particular event where only some partners are involved:

- 16 December 2022, 11:30-12:00 (EPMA-LNEG)
- 21 February 2023, 16:00-17:00 (EPMA-LNEG-TEGnology-RGS-LPRC)
- 15 March 2023, 15:00-15:30 (EPMA-LNEG-GEO)
- 17 April 2023, 15:00-15:30 (EPMA-LNEG-TEGnology-RGS)
- 28 April 2023, 11:00-12:00 (EPMA-LNEG-ASGMI-IGME)

5.8.3 Continuous reporting on Funding&Tender website

The WP Leader (EPMA) is responsible of regularly updating the information on Dissemination and Communication in the relevant section in the project's Continuous Reporting on the Funding&Tender website. There are four pages dedicated to these topics on the portal: "Publications", "Dissemination", "Communication" and "Events and training".

At the latest, an update must be made before the end of each reporting period, as at each periodic report, all the information present in the Continuous Reporting section will be automatically compiled to create Part A of the Periodic Technical Report.

For the moment, only the Publications page has been updated (Figure 33): the publications uploaded on the Zenodo platform have been automatically imported.

The "Dissemination", "Communication" and "Events and training" pages will be updated later.

101058632 (START) HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01
 Call: HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01
 Topic: HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-07

Project Continuous Report

Publications

Project publications (10 publications)

Show/Hide Filters Clear Filters

Number: Title: Title of the journal or equivalent:
 Type: Authors: PID (publisher version of record):

	Type	Title	Authors	Title of the Journal or equivalent	Number	Peer-reviewed	Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication	PID (Publisher version of record)	PID of deposited publication	Actions
1	Publication in conference proceedi	Presentation of the START project at the 2022 EU-Latin Amer	de Oliveira, Daniel	ZENODO		False	False		10.5281/zenodo.7327407	✖
2	Books/monographs	Starty explains START	START project			False	False			✖
3	Other	COMO GENERAR ELECTRICIDAD A PARTIR DE ESCOMBRERAS MI	Ester Boixereu Vila; Concepción F			False	False			✖
4	Other	RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE - START Newsletter Issue #1	START project			False	False			✖
5	Other	RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE - START Newsletter Issue #2	START project			False	False			✖
6	Other	GREEN ENERGY HARVESTING - STATE OF THE ART	START project			False	True			✖
7	Other	GREEN ENERGY HARVESTING - STATE OF THE ART	START project			False	False		10.5281/zenodo.6906481	✖
8	Other	Presentation of the START project at the 2022 EU-Latin Amer	de Oliveira, Daniel			False	False			✖
9	Other	Presentation of the START project at the World PM2022 Con	Neves, F.			False	False			✖
10	Other	Presentation of the START project at the World PM2022 Con	Neves, F.	ZENODO		False	False		10.5281/zenodo.7326411	✖

* 'open access' means the practice of providing online access to research outputs resulting from actions funded under the Programme, in particular scientific publications and research data, free of charge to the end-user

Validate

Figure 33: Screenshot of the page dedicated to Publications on the Funding&Tender portal.

6 TASK 6.2: TECHNICAL AND SCIENTIFIC DISSEMINATION

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M01 to M48

All partners will submit papers in relevant conferences, congresses, exhibitions, and scientific journals to give information on the results of the START project.

- Relevant EPMA events (for the PM community mainly):
 - The EuroPM and/or WorldPM Congress and Exhibition series (a project booth is foreseen)
 - The EPMA technical seminars by sectors (Functional Materials, Hot Isostatic Pressing, etc.)
 - Sectoral Group meetings, e.g.:
 - European Functional Materials Sectoral Group (EuroFM)
 - European Hot Isostatic Pressing Sectoral Group (EuroHIP)
 - Environment, Health, Quality and Safety Working Group (EHQS).
- International Conference on Thermoelectrics (ICT/ECT/ACT conference series), and other conferences to be defined by the consortium.
- Special dissemination seminars and presentations (webinars or in person) on specific project-related topics:
 - contributions from the consortium
 - selected external speakers
 - ads on dedicated printed or online magazines (e.g., Journal of Degraded and Mining Lands Management, Journal of Environmental Management, Environmental Earth Sciences, Environmental Science and Pollution Research, Mine Water and the Environment...)

External events to communicate to the public and to other scientific and industrial communities and improve the awareness of the energy and sustainability issues in the public: EPMA and other consortium partners will take part in

- At least 2 external events and exhibitions per year
- Possibly Science Festivals and Fairs (e.g., the European Researchers' Night) to communicate the scope of the project and improve the awareness of the energy and sustainability issues in the public.

Specific KPIs will be introduced to quantify the impact of project dissemination.

Publications and presentations in conferences, seminars and congresses are strongly encouraged: all consortium partners should try to organise a technical participation in an event to disseminate a part of the work carried out in START. This will broaden the audience for the project topics and in the end will create the condition for successful exploitation.

Thus, maybe with some exceptions, we expect that during the course of the project almost all partners will submit papers in relevant conferences, congresses, exhibitions, and scientific journals to give information on the results of the START project.

Addressing communities that are outside those already covered by the consortium members activities and by the standard journals, magazines and conferences/events is also rather important

for an innovative project like START. For this reason, the plan is to try addressing external communities by publishing well balanced papers and articles in more general magazines, or news services/websites (the Horizon Results, the Horizon Magazine, also suitable generic magazines, like for instance the Open Access Government magazine).

6.1 EVENTS LIST

In order to select the events where the partners, individually or as consortium, should take part, and take materials concerning the project, a “**START Events List**” is established and regularly updated by the WP6 leader (EPMA) on the START SharePoint and every partner will collaborate by giving information on possible events.

In this Excel file, the following information is collected for each event:

- Name of Event
- Priority: the partners are asked to evaluate what is the priority to give to this event in order to try maximising the impact by optimising the effort.
- Date of start of event
- Date of end of event
- Physical/Online/Hybrid: if available, information on the type of participation requested.
- Website: where possible, the link to obtain fresh info about the event
- Location: where the event will be held (in case, “online”)
- Type of audience: scientific (what sector), industrial (what sector), general (what composition) etc.
- START Booth: whether a START booth should be present at the event
- Partner Booth: whether a START partner booth should be present at the event (including name of partner)
- START lectures/papers: in case a presentation is given, details on the topic (e.g., “Generic project presentation” or a specific topic)
- START lecture/paper date: when the presentation will happen
- Presenter: who is going to present
- Reference partner: the partner who will be coordinating the participation
- Attendees: expected number of attendees

The list is the basis for discussion, in the meetings, about participation at the various events.

In Figure 34 the present status of the list is shown.

Event	Priority (1=high)	Date start	Date end	Physical /Online/ Hybrid	Website	Location	Type of audience	START Booth	Partner Booth	START lectures/papers	START lecture/paper date	Presenter	Reference partner	Attendees
EIT Raw Materials Summit (every year around April/May)	-	2022, May		Physical	https://www.eitrmsummit.com/									
EGU - European Geoscience Union (every year around April/May)	-	2022, May		Physical	https://www.egu.eu/									
PDAC - Prospectors & Developers Association of Canada	-	2022, Jun		Physical	https://www.pdac.ca/									
Sustainable Minerals '22	1.50	11/07/2022	13/07/2022	Online	https://mei.eventsair.com/sustainable-minerals-22/									
1st Scientific-Technical Conference of the Geological and Mining Institute of Spain - National center	1.00	12/07/2022	13/07/2022	Physical	https://www.iigme.es/PagInicio2014/fotos/	Madrid (Spain)	IGME-CISC internal			presentation		E. Boixereu i Vila	IGME-CSIC	
Desafíos para la gestión sostenible de los pasivos ambientales mineros/ ECLAC-CEPAL United Nations	1.00	01/08/2022	04/08/2022	Physical	https://www.cepal.org/es/temas/eventos	Perú	Mining companies, Geological Surveys, academia, SMEs			presentation	01/08/2022	Freddy Guzman, Ch	ASGMI	
The Ceramics Expo 2022	1.00	29/08/2022	31/08/2022	Physical	https://www.ceramicsexpousa.com/	Huntington Convention Center of Cleveland, Ohio (USA)	PM community	-	GeniCore					
International Materials, Applications and Technologies (IMAT) - ASM 2022	1.00	12/09/2022	15/09/2022	Physical	https://www.asminternational.org/web/Im	New Orleans, Louisiana (USA)	PM community, Academic	-	GeniCore			Damian Karpowicz		
European Conference on Thermolectrics (ECT) 2022	2.00	14/09/2022	16/09/2022	Physical	https://www.ect2022barcelona.org	Barcelona (Spain)	Thermolectric Academic			to be considered for the following years				
Perumim 35 mining convention	1.00	26/09/2022	30/09/2022	Physical	https://perumim.com	Arequipa (Peru)	Mining companies, Geological Surveys, academia, SMEs			banner at the EC booth			ASGMI	
WorldPM22	1.00	09/10/2022	13/10/2022	Physical	https://www.worldpm2022.com/	Lyon (France)	PM community	Yes	-	EuroFM sectoral Group meeting	11/12/2022	F. Neves	EPMA	
WorldPM22	1.00	09/10/2022	13/10/2022	Physical	https://www.worldpm2022.com/	Lyon (France)	PM community	Yes	-	Industry Corner	11/12/2022	F. Neves	EPMA	
WorldPM22	1.00	09/10/2022	13/10/2022	Physical	https://www.worldpm2022.com/	Lyon (France)	PM community	-	GeniCore	Booth				
WorldPM22	1.00	09/10/2022	13/10/2022	Physical	https://www.worldpm2022.com/	Lyon (France)	PM community	-	MBN	Booth				
IV EDITION MMH, Sustainable Mining	-	18/10/2022	20/10/2022	Physical	https://mmhseville.com/mineria-sostenible	Sevilla (Spain)	Mining					D. de Oliveira	CSIC	
EU-Latin America convention	1.00	03/11/2022	04/11/2022	Physical	https://www.mineralplatform.eu/events/eu-latin-america-convention-raw-materials					Presentation	04/11/2022	D. de Oliveira	ASGMI	
EU-Latin America policy dialogue on the identification of strategic and critical Raw Materials resources	1.00	02/11/2022	03/11/2022	Physical	https://www.mineralplatform.eu/events/eu-latin-america-convention-raw-materials							D. de Oliveira	ASGMI	
Science and Innovation Week 2022	1.00	07/11/2022	11/11/2022	Physical	https://www.semanacienciaMadrid.org/	Madrid (Spain)	General public				10/11/2022	Ester Boixereu	IGME	
Raw Materials Week 2022 (every year in November)	1.00	14/11/2022	18/11/2022	Physical	https://www.eurawmaterialsweek.eu/2022/	Brussels (Belgium)	Raw materials/mining			poster, video			LPRC, SINTEF	
II Extraordinary General Assembly of ASGMI	1.00	14/11/2022	18/11/2022	Physical		Barcelona (Spain)	Geological Surveys Directors		banner, video			G. Olivenza	ASGMI	
1st START Webinar (LNEG)	1.00	28/02/2023	28/02/2023	Online	START website	-	All	-	-	Project pres	28/02/2023	F. Neves	LNEG	
1st START Webinar (LNEG)	1.00	28/02/2023	28/02/2023	Online	START website	-	Raw materials/mining	-	-	Technical pres	28/02/2023	D. Oliveira	LNEG	
GENERA 2023 (International Energy and Environment Fair)	2.00	21/02/2023	23/02/2023	Physical	https://www.ifeima.es/en/genera	Madrid (Spain)	Energy and Environment							
PDAC 2023: The World's Premier Mineral Exploration & Mining Convention	1.00	05/03/2023	08/03/2023	Physical	https://www.pdac.ca/convention	Toronto (Canada)	Raw materials/mining							LNEG
Sourcing the European energy transition from domestic resources - vision or wishful thinking?	1.00	25/04/2023	26/04/2023	Physical	https://www.greenpee.eu/news.html	Uppsala, Sweden	Raw materials/mining							GEO
2nd START Webinar (LNEG)	1	26/04/2023	26/04/2023	Online										LNEG
EGU - European Geoscience Union (every year around April/May)	-	23/04/2023	28/04/2023	Physical	https://www.egu.eu/	Vienna (Austria)	Raw materials/mining							
EIT Raw Materials Summit (every year around April/May)	-	15/05/2023	17/05/2023	Physical	https://www.eitrmsummit.com/	Brussels (Belgium)	Raw materials/mining							
Arminera	1.67	22/05/2023	24/05/2023	Physical	https://arminera.ar.messefrankfurt.com/bu	Buenos Aires (Argentina)	Energy, Transport & logistic, Mining Technology and industrial fairs							ASGMI
3rd START Webinar (LNEG)	1	31/05/2023	31/05/2023	Online										LNEG
European Sustainable Energy Week and EUSEW Fair	1.00	20/06/2023	22/06/2023	Hybrid	https://sustainable-energy-week.ec.europa	Brussels (Belgium)	Energy and Environment	Yes	-					EPMA
Annual International Conference on Thermolectrics (ICT)	1.00	21/06/2023	25/06/2023	Physical	https://web.cvent.com/event/89985a9c-7c	Seattle (USA)	Thermolectrics							8000
Jornadas Científico Técnicas del IGME-CSIC	1.00	2023, Jun?			www.csic.es							Ester Boixereu	IGME	
Sustainable Minerals '23	n.d.	07/06/2023	09/06/2023	Physical	https://mei.eventsair.com/sustainable-min	Falmouth (UK)	Raw materials/mining							
Euronanoforum2023	1.67	11/06/2023	13/06/2023	Physical	https://mkon.nu/euro_nano_forum_2023	Malmö (Sweden)								
EPMA FM seminar 2023	1.00	28/06/2023	29/06/2023	Hybrid	seminars.epma.com	San Sebastián (Spain)	PM community	-	-	Technical pres		?	EPMA	
PM/AM/Metform on PM materials for Energy	1.00	05/07/2023	07/07/2023	Physical		Dresden (Germany)	PM community	-	-	Technical pres		?	EPMA	
EPMA Summer School 2023	1	17/07/2023	21/07/2023	Physical	https://summerschool.epma.com/	Dresden (Germany)	PM community	-	-	The START project/PM thermolectrics		H. Yin/A. Bianchin	EPMA	
RawMat 2023	n.d.	28/08/2023	02/09/2023	Physical	https://www.rawmat2023.gr/congress/	Athens (Greece)								
4th START Webinar (LNEG)	n.d.	2023, Sep?		Online										LNEG
European Conference on Thermolectrics (ECT) 2023?	n.d.	18/09/2023	21/09/2023	Physical	https://thermolectric-conference.eu/	Prague, CZ	Thermolectric Academic							TEGNOLOGY?
SPM event - Materials for Energy Transition	n.d.	06/09/2023	08/09/2023	Physical	https://spmaterials.pt/site/materials-for-er	Oporto, P	Materials							LNEG
European Roundtable on Sustainable Consumption and Production	n.d.	2023, Sep?		Physical	https://erscp2021.eu/	Wageningen, NL	Academic, wide							LNEG
Researchers' Night 2023	n.d.	29/09/2023	30/09/2023	Hybrid	https://marie-skłodowska-curie-actions.ec	Many	Academic, wide	-	-	?		?		
EuroPM23	n.d.	01/10/2023	04/10/2023	Physical	Europm2023.com	Libon (Portugal)	PM community	Yes	-	Technical pres?		?	EPMA	
Raw Materials Week 2023 (every year in November)	n.d.	2023, Nov		Physical										

Figure 34: Status of the START Events List Excel file (updated 10/05/2023) for the initial part of the project. In light green the events covered.

The tool is updated about upcoming events, reassessing the priorities continuously. In general, some high priority recurring events are these:

- European Conference on Thermoelectrics (ECT) conference series
- GENERA (International Energy and Environment Fair)
- Raw Materials Week
- EIT Raw Materials summit
- EU-Latin America Convention on Raw Materials
- EU Green week
- EPMA's EuroPM Powder Metallurgy yearly Congress & Exhibition (was World PM in 2022)
- EPMA's seminars (HIP, Functional Materials)
- Sustainable Minerals
- In general, when partners have large internal events, these will be covered.

6.2 EVENTS COVERED IN M07-M12

After a very strong activity in the first 6 months in terms of participation in events, this task was not so active in December 2022 and January 2023, that are not so lively in terms of events.

An event was originally thought to be interesting, the GENERA 2023 (international Energy and Environment Fair) in Madrid on 21st-23rd February 2023: but the partners most involved in the industrial side and generally the consortium preferred to postpone participation in this kind of events, more related to the application, to later years in the project, when more practical achievements could be shown in order to attract interest.

Another event that the consortium had singled out for participation was the European Sustainable Energy Week and EUSEW Fair, 20th-22nd June 2023. In particular, the consortium had applied to be granted a booth in the EUSEW Fair. It was envisaged of showing also a demo of waste heat recovery, a device that TEGnology, one of the consortium partners, normally uses already in exhibitions to highlight the working principle of their devices. Unfortunately, that fair hosts a limited number of booths, and this year a large number of applications was received by organizers (surely more than 91 as this was the sequential number received while applying), and finally START was not selected for the fair. A new application will be made next year, possibly with even more appealing material.

6.2.1 PDAC 2023, *The World's Premier Mineral Exploration & Mining Convention, Toronto (Canada), 5th-8th March 2023*

The project was present at the PDAC (Prospectors and Developers Association of Canada)⁹ 2023 edition, which took place in the Toronto Convention Centre from 5th to 8th March. The event, one of the largest events in the mining sector, attracted almost 24000 attendees from 133 countries, 2500 investors, and hosted 1050 exhibitors¹⁰.

⁹ <https://www.pdac.ca/convention>

¹⁰ <https://www.pdac.ca/convention/attendee-info/past-conventions/2023-convention>

Figure 35: Audience in one of the sessions at PDAC 2023 (source: PDAC website).

Figure 36: Exhibition at PDAC 2023 (source: PDAC website).

A continuous presentation outlining the projects objectives and goals was shown during the event in the EU booth. This presentation generated interest amongst visitors.

Figure 37 the EU booth that hosted START.

Figure 38 Presentation about START on show at the PDAC 2023

6.2.2 ASGMI General Assembly Santo Domingo (Dominican Republic), 17th-21st April

ASGMI held its General Assembly from April 17th to 21st in Santo Domingo (Dominican Republic). During the Assembly, a workshop was held on "The role of geological services in the ecological and energy transition," and there were talks from the different participating geological services on the state of the art in the identification and characterization of critical minerals in their respective countries, among other topics.

The Vice President of the Government, Raquel Peña, and the Minister of Energy and Mines of the Dominican Republic attended the opening ceremony. Also, the Minister of Mining of Guatemala and representatives from international institutions that are not part of ASGMI, such as UNEP and USGS, joined the event.

During the talks, the activity report of ASGMI's expert groups was presented, specifically the groups on mining environmental liabilities and mineral resources participating in the START project. The project was discussed, the presentation video was shared, and the next webinar, the second START free webinar, which was held the following week, was announced.

Figure 39 G. Olivenza (ASGMI) attended the ASGMI General Assembly in the Dominican Republic.

Figure 40: Delegates at the ASGMI General Assembly in the Dominican Republic.

6.2.3 *International Conference “Sourcing the European energy transition from domestic resources – vision or wishful thinking”, Uppsala (Sweden), 25-26th April 2023*

START was present also in this conference, hosted by the EU HORIZON 2020 project GREENPEG, in cooperation with the Swedish Association of Mines, Minerals and Metal Producers (SVEMIN) and the European Technology Platform on Sustainable Mineral Resources (ETP SMR) in Uppsala, in 25th-26th April. Some informative material and a rollup about the project were exhibited.

Figure 41: START banner on display at the GREENPEG Conference in Uppsala.

Around 100 participants from all around the globe were attending the conference. Part of the conference was about topics regarding the EU's Green deal and how the actual geopolitical situation is affecting global supply chains. The START project attracted the interest of attendees based on the fact that waste material like domestically sourced tetrahedrite could fill gaps in those supply chains.

GREENPEG invited the START consortium to give more detailed information in the form of a webinar in the near future.

6.2.4 EPMA General Assembly 2023, Brussels and hybrid, 27th April 2023 – and other events

During the General Assembly of the European Powder Metallurgy Association (EPMA), F. Neves (LNEG) gave a thorough presentation of about 30' to present the project in detail, with a focus on the powder metallurgy content in the project, to address the interests of the audience, about 30 people consisting of members of the association and a few invited speakers. The event was held in a hybrid format on 27th April 2023, with some participants in Brussels (legal address of the EPMA), and some connected remotely. In addition to that, in the morning B. Vicenzi (EPMA) had showed in a slide the main features of the project whilst reviewing the activity of the association in EU funded projects.

Figure 42: A screenshot taken during F. Neves presentation in the EPMA General Assembly 2023.

Additionally, the two technical managers of EPMA have given information about the activities of START during the seminars held in early 2023, namely the Hot Isostatic Pressing seminar in Dresden (8th-9th March 2023), the Press&Sinter seminar in Barcelona (28th-29th March 2023) and the Metal Injection Moulding seminar in Sandviken, Sweden (24th-25th May 2023). In the latter occasions, some promotional materials about START (leaflet and the issue of Powder Metallurgy Review containing the article on the project) was also available to the about 25 delegates (Figure 43 and Figure 44).

Figure 43: Among the literature available for the participants in the EPMA seminar “Progress and Challenges in Press&Sinter” held in Barcelona (Spain) on 28th-29th March 2023 there

was also the START flyer (bottom row, right), and copies of the Powder Metallurgy Review Spring 2023 issue, containing an article on START.

Figure 44: Among the literature available for the participants at the EPMA seminar “Materials and Improvement in Metal Injection Moulding” held in Sandviken (Sweden) on 24th-25th May 2023 there was also the START flyer.

6.3 EVENTS IN PREPARATION

In the next months, participation in some events has already been organised:

- A training lecture on “Thermoelectric Materials and the START Project” is foreseen at the EPMA Powder Metallurgy Summer School that will take place in Dresden, at the Fraunhofer IFAM, from 17th to 21st July 2023. Details will be given in Deliverable D6.4, that is due at the end of May 2023 as well.
- A booth will be again prepared at the EPMA Euro PM2023 Congress & Exhibition that will be held in Lisbon, from 1st to 4th October 2023, with similar effort as in 2022, and possibly with

some more participation from other partners, namely the Portuguese partners in the consortium, due to the location in Lisbon.

- Information about START project (video presentation) will be available at the booth of the "EU-LATAM Mining Platform" within the ARMINERA mining fair (22nd-24th May 2023, Buenos Aires) where members of the consortium (ASGMI, IGME-CSIC) will be present.

Other smaller events where project partners will bring information and short presentations about the project will surely be attended, as happened last year in the same period of the year.

6.4 PUBLICATIONS

In the first 6 months of the project, as documented in Deliverable D6.3, a few documents had been produced for publication:

- A short document (3 pages) made available also on the project's website, and also hosted in SlideShare, that is titled "Green energy harvesting - State of the art"¹¹. It was prepared by LNEG in July 2022.
- A 22-pages pdf of the presentation given by F. Neves (LNEG), START coordinator, at the EPMA World PM2022 Powder Metallurgy World Congress and Exhibition in October 2022¹².
- A 21-pages pdf of the presentation given by D. de Oliveira (LNEG), at the EU-Latin America Partnership on Raw Materials in November 2022¹³.
- The 11-pages pdf of Issue 1 of the START Newsletter "RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE"³

All these publications have been uploaded on the website and on the Zenodo open access repository, where a "community" named "Sustainable energy harvesting systems based on innovative mine waste recycling" was created. A DOI has been obtained for each, and they have automatically been added in the Continuous Reporting Publications page in the Funding & Tender portal for the project (see chapter 5.8.3).

In this second half of the first year, some other documents were uploaded to Zenodo:

- "Como generar electricidad a partir de escombreras mineras", the slides of the presentation on the START project, in Spanish, that was given by Ester Boixereu Vila (IGME-CSIC) on November 10, 2022, at the headquarters of the professional association of Spanish geologists (ICOG), in Madrid, during the "Semana de la Ciencia y la Innovacion" (Science and Innovation Week).
- the Issue #2 of the Newsletter¹⁴, described in chapter 5.5.2, and visible in the Annex I.

In addition to this, some publications on magazines have been obtained, as reported in the following chapters. These have not been uploaded to Zenodo, yet they are fully readable online, with open access, in the magazines' websites. Details are in the following chapters.

¹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6906481>

¹² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7326411>

¹³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7327407>

¹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7925963>

6.4.1 *START on the magazine “Powder Metallurgy Review”*

As anticipated in deliverable D6.3, an article written by the consortium, with contributions from F. Neves (LNEG), B. Vicenzi (EPMA), A. Bianchin (MBN Nanomaterialia), M. Rosinski (GeniCore) and H. Yin (TEGnology) was published on the Spring 2023 issue (vol. 12, n.1, Figure 45) of the well-known powder metallurgical magazine Powder Metallurgy Review¹⁵.

The Powder Metallurgy Review is published quarterly in print and digital formats, distributed upon subscription, e-newsletters and dedicated social media networks (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn), at numerous industry events worldwide (RAPID-TCT in Chicago, as well as a number of other spring events), and indefinitely available on the magazine website. The target is the powder metallurgy community, thus within groups 2 and 3 in our target segmentation (component manufacturers, end-users, industry suppliers, analysts, researchers), with possible outreach also in groups 1 and 4 because of the free web visibility. According to the publisher, the average circulation per issue of Powder Metallurgy Review over the last year is well above 10000, mostly as online/pdf.

On page 89, the paper titled "The START project: Creating a sustainable supply chain for green energy harvesting products by Powder Metallurgy" includes an overview of START's motivation, approach, goals and expected impact, and, targeting the magazine's usual audience within the powder metallurgy community, more details into the powder metallurgy side of the project: how to derive powders from the tetrahedrite containing minerals and pure elements (by Mechanochemical Synthesis), and how to consolidate them (by Pulse Plasma Compaction) into functional materials and devices with good thermoelectric properties. Some initial data and images coming from the ongoing tasks are shown. The full paper is visible in Annex II.

¹⁵ <https://www.pm-review.com>

Figure 45: The Spring 2023 issue cover (Spring 2023, 112 pages) of the Powder Metallurgy Review printed and web magazine.

The full issue is published Open Access, and it is freely available for reading and downloading in pdf version on the Powder Metallurgy Review website:

<https://www.pm-review.com/powder-metallurgy-review-archive/powder-metallurgy-review-spring-2023-vol-12-no-1/>

6.4.2 *START on the magazine “água&ambiente”*

A Portuguese magazine dealing with the environment (energy, waste and water issues), “água & ambiente”, with about 1200 printed copies, hosted an article (in Portuguese) about our project in its November-December 2022 issue¹⁶. The original title was “Projeto START vai transformar residuos de minas em produtos para dispositivos termoeletricos” (“The START project will

¹⁶ <https://www.ambienteonline.pt/jornal/edicao-247-novembro-dezembro-2022>

transform mine wastes into thermoelectric devices”). It is a detailed interview with our coordinator F. Neves (LNEG) that fills page 48 and 49 of the magazine. The article is visible in Annex III.

6.4.3 START on the magazine “Ingenium”

The magazine “Ingenium” published by the Ordem dos Engenheiros (the Portuguese Professional Public Association of Engineers), that is distributed to all members of that association (around 60000) hosted a short info, in Portuguese, about the project in its April-May-June 2023 issue n. 180, page 114¹⁷. The main features of START were summarized and a link to our website was given.

Figure 46 The news about START in Ingenium, n.180, p.114.

¹⁷ <https://www.ordemengenheiros.pt/pt/centro-de-informacao/publicacoes/revista-ingenium/ingenium-n-180-edicao-de-abril-maio-e-junho-de-2023/>

7 TASK 6.3: TRAINING ACTIVITIES

Task leader: EPMA; Participants: All; M12 to M48

This task's activities started officially in May 2023. The details are not reported here, but in Deliverable D6.4, that is also due at the end of May 2023.

8 TASK 6.4: CLUSTERING

Task leader: ASGMI; Participants: All; M03 to M48

The objective of the clustering activity, that constitutes task T6.4 and began at M03 and will continue for the whole project duration to end at M48, is building a comprehensive cluster for the dissemination of the project. The main idea is to create an effective strategy to identify similar and interesting projects and find synergies to create value, avoid duplications and strengthen and maximize the START project results impact.

Projects that share a common theme or address similar challenges can form a cluster initiative and deliver shared strategic outputs. Thus, START wants to enhance links and synergies with such projects and initiatives. ASGMI with the support of all partners is identifying the project coordinators of the selected projects & initiatives. Mapping the synergies among the different projects will maximize the impact and contribute to have a more efficient and strong European Innovation.

A database has been created, which has been filled during this period with interesting initiatives and projects and will be kept updated throughout the rest of the project. Some of the resources consulted to feed this database are the following:

- The Community Research and Development Information Service (CORDIS) for H2020 or Horizon Europe projects
- The EIT (including the KICs on Raw Materials, InnoEnergy & Climate KIC)
- The internal community (partners in the consortium and its members)

The links are being established by a series of online short meetings with the relevant Project Coordinators or key people and the START project coordinator and/or the Communication WP leader.

Key events and meetings are essential to identify and establish good connections: the people from the initiatives in the clustering database, likely belonging to the audience target Groups 2 and 3, but in some cases also from Group 1, will be invited to the relevant events organized by START (seminars, webinars, trainings, final event) ensuring dedicated time for networking and collaboration. Conversely, START consortium members participating to events are supposed to seek connections with all interesting stakeholders.

8.1 CLUSTERING STRATEGY

A clustering strategy has been designed in order to be implemented during the whole project duration. This strategy consists of two work lines: internal and external clustering:

8.1.1 *Internal clustering*

Consortium members are being contacted to identify projects, or other initiatives in which they are involved and/or are aware of, and check if they have common points and potential to establish synergies.

8.1.2 *External clustering*

The strategy for external clustering consists in contacting institutions and organizations that are not directly involved in the START project but work in similar or complementary themes.

These can be classified as explained in the next subchapters.

8.1.2.1 Key institutions and actors

Associations and big organizations directly or indirectly related to technical projects or other research initiatives are especially important because networks in which they are involved have a big potential for clustering with START project. They have a “helicopter view” of the activities done by their members and contacting them is a fast and easy way to reach a large number of potential projects.

Key people (outreach people and project leaders) in these organizations have been identified and contacted in order to schedule meetings between projects or work package leaders.

Clustering task and communication leaders of the project have already contacted key people in EIT Raw Materials and InnoEnergy KICs, and EuroGeoSurveys.

Some initial meetings have already taken place.

During this period, connection has been established with the ERHASE Cluster initiative. The ERHASE Cluster is formed by three European Projects (FAST-SMART, SYMPHONY, InComEss) with the aim to address the technical scope areas within the context of energy harvesting and storage technologies. Through the cluster, participating projects may expand their impact beyond the project level, while contributing to the dissemination of state-of-the-art research and developments. Together, the 3 projects will boost awareness regarding the research outcomes and promote energy harvesting with relevant stakeholders, such as academia and industry.

A meeting with the ERHASE cluster has been scheduled with the aim to discuss inclusion of START.

8.1.2.2 Link with communication and dissemination activities

Project consortium members participation in technical or commercial big events, congress or other initiatives is interesting because this participation brings the opportunity to meet key people and find out new projects or initiatives related directly or indirectly with the project in order to stablish synergies.

To maximize the potential of clustering in these events, the clustering strategy builds a list of the events in which the consortium members are going to attend, identify potential organizations or key participants in the event and suggest to the consortium members to contact them before and during the events to talk about related projects. This list is actually included in the Events List for Dissemination and the most interesting events for clustering are given a higher priority.

8.1.2.3 CORDIS

CORDIS provides information on all EU-supported R&D activities, including programs (Horizon Europe, H2020, FP7 and older), projects, results and publications so is an essential platform for looking for projects under same or similar calls and finding out the coordinator to establish contact.

8.1.2.4 *Data base creation*

A database has been created to list the clustering actions (see chapter 8.1.3).

This database includes data such as the name or organization, contact person, date of meeting and comments related to experiences exchanged in the meeting.

8.1.2.5 *Invite key actors to project meetings*

Project meeting or events (virtual and in person) are good opportunities for inviting key actors (project leaders, researchers or stakeholders) to disseminate the objectives and advances in the project and try to establish synergies and common dissemination actions. Some of these researchers have been invited as speakers in the webinars organized by the project and have contributed to their dissemination and diffusion:

- Webinar #02 (26th April 2023):
 - Fredy Guzmán-Martínez (Servicio Geológico Mexicano)
 - Rafael Bittencourt Lima (Serviço Geológico do Brasil – CPRM)
- Webinar #03 (31st May 2023):
 - Doug Crane (DTP Thermoelectrics LLC, also member of START's Scientific Advisory Board)
 - Julie Hollies (EuroGeoSurveys, also member of START's Scientific Advisory Board)

More will be invited in the future.

8.1.3 *Clustering database*

As already mentioned, a clustering database has been created in order to achieve the objectives of the clustering strategy. Database is being completed with new organizations and projects and will remain active throughout the project.

Key institutions and interesting related projects identified so far are shown in Table 5. As this deliverable is public, but the full list cannot be public for privacy issues, it is not shown here. Only stakeholder entities' names are shown in the table.

Table 5: Key institutions and interesting related project identified for Clustering.

Organization	Meeting date	Projects	
EIT Raw Materials	16/11/2022	EuGeLi	https://eitrawmaterials.eu/project/eugeli/
		RIS-CuRE	RIS-CuRE: Zero waste recovery of copper tailings in the ESEE region - EIT RawMaterials
		BioLeach	BioLeach: Innovative Bio-treatment of RM - EIT RawMaterials
		INCO-Piles 2020	INCO-Piles-2020. International consortium to recover CRMs from stockpiles/tailings targeting RIS - EIT RawMaterials
EIT InnoEnergy	To be scheduled		

H2020 and Horizon Europe Projects		
FutuRaM	To be scheduled	https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058522

In addition to what reported in the table, the project GREENPEG that organised the Uppsala conference mentioned in 6.2.3, has expressed the intention of inviting START to give information in a later webinar, to be defined.

8.2 KEY EVENTS AND MEETINGS

During this first period of the START project, the consortium members have participated in different events in which they have disseminated about the project, its main objectives and topics.

In these events, members have had the opportunity to seek connections with interesting stakeholders.

Main events that have described with more details in 7.1 are listed below:

- 1st scientific-technical conference of the geological and mining institute of Spain-National Center, Madrid (Spain) 12th-13th July 2022
- CEPAL Regional Event, Miraflores (Peru), 1st-4th Aug 2022: “Challenges for sustainable management of Mining Environmental Liabilities (MELs)”.
- PERUMIN 2022, Arequipa (Perú), 26th-30th Sep 2022
- International Workshop in Geochemistry, Medellín (Colombia), 19th-23rd Sep 2022
- World PM 2022, Lyon (France), 9th-13th Oct 2022
- EU-Latin America Raw Materials Convention and UE-Latin America Policy Dialogue on the identification of strategic and critical raw materials resources, Santiago de Chile (Chile), 2nd-4th Nov 2022
- Raw Materials Week, Brussels (Belgium), 14th-18th Nov 2022
- II Extraordinary General Assembly of ASGMI, Barcelona (Spain), 14th-18th Nov 2022
- PDAC 2023, The World’s Premier Mineral Exploration & Mining Convention, Toronto (Canada), 5th – 8th March 2023
- XVII General Assembly of ASGMI, Santo Domingo (República Dominicana), 17th-21st April 2023
- International Conference “Sourcing the European energy transition from domestic resources-vision or wishful thinking”, Uppsala (Sweden), 25-26th April 2023
- EPMA General Assembly 2023, Brussels and hybrid, 27th April 2023 and other events (seminars held in early 2023, namely the Hot Isostatic Pressing seminar in Dresden from 8th to 9th of March and the Press&Sinter seminar in Barcelona from 28th to 29th of March).
- EU-Latin America Raw Materials Convention and 2nd EU-Latin America Policy Dialogue on the identification of strategic and critical raw materials resources, Buenos Aires (Argentina), 22nd –24th May 2023

9 TASK 6.5: FINAL EVENT

Task leader: ASGMI; Participants: LNEG, All; M42 to M48

A final conference will be organised at the end of the project as a main dissemination event showcasing the successes achieved over the four years of the project.

The conference will likely take place in Brussels.

The details of the event (type of event, audience, keynote speakers...) will be determined during the project (starting around M42).

The final conference will try to be organised back-to-back with another mayor relevant event to ensure as large attendance as possible.

This task is not active yet. Nothing to report.

10 ANNEX I – START NEWSLETTER – ISSUE #2 – MAY 2022

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7925963

BIANNUAL NEWSLETTER OF THE START PROJECT | ISSUE 2

RECOVER-REFORM-REUSE

for a Sustainable Future

EDITORIAL

Dear members of the START community,

Welcome to the second issue of the START project Newsletter! In this issue, we will share with you some highlights from our recent events and activities, and you will learn more about START with STARTY, our friendly robot that helps us explain the project scope. We

will also introduce you to the members of our Scientific Advisory Board (SAB), who provide us with valuable guidance and feedback on our work. They are:

- Doug Crane: Chief Technology Officer (CTO) of DTP Thermoelectrics and former Director of Thermoelectric Engineering at Alphabet Energy, Inc.
- Jean-Yves Escabasse: Chemical Engineer and Doctor with 40 years of experience in R&D and innovation within several materials industry sectors.
- Julie Hollis: Secretary General of EuroGeoSurveys (EGS) – The Geological Surveys of Europe.

We are very grateful for their support and welcome them on this journey! In this issue, we have an exclusive interview with Julie Hollis, where she presents the mission and objectives of the EuroGeoSurveys (EGS) and the contribution to the EU priorities related with the Green Deal and the EU Action Plan on Critical Raw Materials (CRM). She also shares her views on the EU's resilience towards CRM security and the possible synergies between EGS and START.

In addition, we have two technical pills for you: one related to the geology of tetrahedrites (the main mineral used in START) and another describing the use of powder technology for processing tetrahedrites into high-performance thermoelectric materials. Finally, we will take you on a tour around two of our consortium partners: TEGnology (from Denmark) and RGS Development (from the Netherlands), both small enterprises that develop innovative thermoelectric solutions for different sectors.

We hope you enjoy reading this Newsletter and we invite you to stay tuned for more updates from START on our website and social media channels.

(F. Neves)

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Co-funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Figure 47: START-Newsletter_Issue_2-page-001

STARTY – 2: THE GEOLOGY WORK IN START

2 GEOLOGY

2050

EUROPE HAS THE INTENTION OF BECOMING THE WORLD'S FIRST CLIMATE-NEUTRAL CONTINENT BY 2050, WHICH MEANS IMPLEMENTING THE 'EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL'.

TO ACHIEVE THIS (GREEN) ENERGY TRANSITION, MINERAL RESOURCES ARE CRUCIAL, MOSTLY DRIVEN BY DEMAND IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES AND BY GREEN ENERGY TECHNOLOGIES.

ACCESS TO SUSTAINABLE RESOURCES IS A KEY FOR STRENGTHENING THE EUROPEAN RESILIENCE IN RELATION TO RAW MATERIALS AND ACHIEVING THE NEEDED RESOURCES' SECURITY REQUIRES SEVERAL ACTIONS.

MINERAL RAW MATERIALS ARE CRUCIAL TO THE EUROPEAN ECONOMY. TECHNOLOGICAL PROGRESS RELIES ON ACCESS TO A GROWING NUMBER OF RAW MATERIALS.

2050

NEUTRALITY

SECURITY

CLIMATE

ATMOSPHERE

CARBON

EMISSIONS

WORLD

RENEWABLE

GREEN

ACTION

RESOURCES

EUROPE

TECHNOLOGIES

WIND TURBINES

ELECTRIC MOTORS

BATTERIES

POWER GRIDS

RAW MATERIALS

ENERGY STORAGE

SOLAR PANELS

MAGNETS

WIRING

HARDWARE

THERMOELECTRICS

Figure 48: START-Newsletter_Issue_2-page-002

Figure 49: START-Newsletter_Issue_2-page-003

Figure 50: START-Newsletter_Issue_2-page-004

START CHRONICLES: GEOLOGY AND MORE

NEWS FROM WORK PACKAGE 2 "SELECTION OF MINE WASTE SITES; PHYSICAL MINERALS SEPARATION AND CONCENTRATION": TETRAHEDRITES COLLECTED IN SLOVAKIA HAVE BEEN ANALYSED AND SUCCESSFULLY CONCENTRATED

One of the countries where START is looking for tetrahedrites in mining sites is Slovakia. The partner Štátny Geologický ústav Dionýza Štúra (State Geological Institute of Dionýz Štúr, SGUDS), one of the partners working in START's Work Package 2, has reviewed the Strieborná vein deposit in Rožňava and analysed the samples collected there (Figure 1), and finally attempted to separate the tetrahedrite with a few different methods.

Figure 1 - (a) Strieborná mine, (b) mineral vein (c) raw sample after the homogenization and quartering (after the first crushing degree).

The Strieborná vein deposit of the Rožňava ore field (ROF) is situated at the south-eastern margin of the Western Carpathian basement units, inside the Gelnica Group formation of the Gemeric Superunit. The Early Paleozoic Gelnica Group forms the oldest sequence of the metasedimentary/metavolcanitic formations of the Gemeric Superunit. The ROF area is penetrated by the subparallelly arranged hydrothermal siderite-sulphidic veins of SE-NW direction. The history of mining in the ROF started in the 13th century, when the greatest interest was focused mainly on gold, silver, copper, antimony and mercury. In 1981, northwards from the Rožňava mining city, a new Strieborná vein was discovered, and it became the most significant vein structure in the ROF. The vein position was compared with the historically known, parallelly oriented Mária vein. The distance between the Strieborná and Mária veins is 600 m (Figure 2). The vein filling and the structural position in the ore field suggest a close link between the veins origin and structural evolution. The Strieborná vein genesis is the product of multiple epigenetic hydrothermal mineralizations, with a close relationship between the vein filling and rheologically contrasting environment. Consequently, the vein does not crop out on the surface. The largest accumulation is known from the 10th mine horizon (20 m b.s.l.) in the total length of 1300 m. The continuation of the vein gradually decays in the overlying dark black metapelites and grey metasandstones.

Metaclasts often contain layers of quartz and lithic wackes. Below the 10th level (below 0 m a.s.l.) the ore body is situated within metasediments and metavolcanic rocks¹.

Major vein minerals are medium to the coarse-grained siderite of two generations and younger multi-generational quartz-sulphide mineralization of two generations. The most abundant ore minerals are tetrahedrite, chalcopyrite, pyrite and arsenopyrite. Brittle, steel-grey coloured

tetrahedrite, which is the most important ore mineral, is spatially controlled by the older siderite that is in the form of reticulated veins and clusters. A more brittle tetrahedrite variety with steel blue colour and high metallic lustre is usually enriched by Cu, Ag, Bi, Sb and Hg. A darker low lustre variety contains more Zn and Fe. The high content of silver in tetrahedrite was the reason for the name of the Strieborná vein. The concentration of tetrahedrite in the vein bodies has a zonal distribution, and gradually decreases downwards to underlying rocks where it is substituted by pyrite. Quartz is the main gangue mineral and forms several generations. The products of the youngest quartz-sulphide phase are tetrahedrite, kobellite, bismuthinite, bournonite, jamesonite and stibnite.

Figure 2 - Geological cross-section through the NE part of Rožňava-Mária ore segment (Mesaričik et al., 1991 – modified).

- 1 – recrystallized metavolcanics (mafic pyroclastics);
- 2 – metasandstones interbedded by keratophyre metapyroclastics;
- 3 – altered grey metasandstones with black phyllite intercalations;
- 4 – coarse laminated metasandstones intercalated by green-grey phyllites;
- 5 – ore veins;
- 6 – mining levels;
- 7 – prospecting hole;
- 8 – faults;
- 9 – sampling location. The age of volcano-sedimentary complex is Late Paleozoic. The inset shows the location of the Rožňava ore field (ROF).

The raw samples were crushed, homogenized and quartered (Figure 1c), and then crushed again and sieved into several fractions, from below 0.1 mm to above 1 mm (see scheme in Figure 3). After that, both gravity separation and ElectroMagnetic Separation (EMS) were used for concentrating the tetrahedrite in the samples of the different fractions (Figure 4).

Without going into the experimental details, the conclusion was that EMS (dry way), was effective in significantly increasing the tetrahedrite concentration (approximately

80-97 wt%). Additionally, fractions below 0.5 mm show only minor differences in mineralogical composition with the presence of a small amount of accessory minerals.

Thus, on the basis of obtained results all the above-mentioned size fractions of raw sample will be merged and subjected to EMS (dry way) with the aim of obtaining approximately 10 kg of tetrahedrite product that will be used by our project partners to produce the mineral-derived sulphide p-type thermoelectric materials.

Figure 3 - Scheme of the raw mineral sample processing

Figure 4 - Example of obtained concentrate after the EMS process: sample RV-13.

NEWS FROM WORK PACKAGE 3 “MATERIALS MODELLING AND PROCESSING”: ACTIVITY ON MECHANOCHEMICAL SYNTHESIS AND PULSE PLASMA COMPACTION OF TETRAHEDRITES

We will report here on Work Package 3 (WP3), which is dedicated to Materials modelling and Processing. In these first months, the WP3 activities have proceeded along several interconnected paths: (1) experimental modelling (Taguchi method) for the selection of optimum material composition (in terms of transition metal dopants in the tetrahedrite structure) to achieve the best TE efficiency, (2) process optimization for the production of tetrahedrites via mechanochemical synthesis (MCS), (3) optimization of the pulse plasma compaction (PPC) sintering conditions.

Measurements of Seebeck coefficient (S), electrical (α) and thermal conductivity (κ) have been performed on the first sintered samples, to determine the maximum efficiency, expressed by the dimensionless figure of merit, zT, according to the following equation:

$$zT = TS^2 \frac{\alpha}{\kappa}$$

Tetrahedrite-tennantite minerals are p-type thermoelectric materials characterized by very high values of S and extremely low values of κ, the latter is due to their complex unit cells (Figure 5a) and in particular to the out-of-plane vibrational mode of the Cu atom in the Sb[Cu₃]Sb sub-unit shown in Figure 1c, which gives rise to strong phonon-phonon scattering, similarly to other poor thermal conductors such as skutterudites and clathrates².

Figure 5 - (a) tetrahedrite unit cell, (b) coordination sub-units, (c) Sb[Cu₃]Sb trigonal bipyramidal sub-unit, much likely related to the poor thermal conductivity of tetrahedrites. Reproduced from ref. 2.

Of general formula Cu₁₀(TM)₂(Sb,As)₂S₁₃, with TM being transition metals, the tetrahedrite-tennantite crystal structure offers huge potential for compositional variations. Common TMs present in natural mineral tetrahedrites are Fe and Zn, and in lower amounts Pb, Hg, Cd, Mn and others. Synthetic tetrahedrites can be successfully produced with many more different compositions, and zT values ranging from 0.6 for undoped tetrahedrite (TM = Cu), to values higher than 1 for specific combination of dopants have been reported³. The nature and ratio of TMs has a considerable influence on the zT value, that is why the START project (and WP3, in particular) aims at selecting the most efficient composition of dopants and subsequently at producing the tetrahedrite with desired composition from a mixture of mineral and synthetic starting materials, using the highest possible amount of natural tetrahedrite from mine waste.

In these first months of work, we have selected two compositions, reported to have high TE efficiency, and have optimized the synthesis parameters of MCS (Figure 6), obtaining monophasic doped tetrahedrites as fine powder materials. Several PPC sintering trials have been performed on the powder tetrahedrites, and the first measures of zT have already given promising values.

Meanwhile, material modelling is ongoing, the Taguchi method is being employed as an experimental modelling tool for researching other dopant compositions, with the aim of identifying compositions with even higher TE efficiency.

The next steps of WP3 will focus on the mechanochemical synthesis of natural/synthetic tetrahedrites (maximizing the amount of mineral from mine waste). The composition of each mineral sample will be accurately analyzed and later adjusted by addition of the elements required to target the desired composition. On these powder materials, the optimized PPC sintering protocol will be applied and zT at different temperatures will be evaluated, from the measurements of α , κ and S .

Figure 6 - Mixing of the powder elements for mechanochemical synthesis (left), MCS reactor facility at MBN (center) and sintered pellets by GeniCore (right).

START'S SCIENTIFIC ADVISORY BOARD APPOINTED

In November 2022, the START project consortium revealed the members of its Scientific Advisory Board (SAB). It is an external consulting body, appointed by the consortium's Executive Committee, consisting of experts from public/private organizations representing the scientific community involved in the project topics. According to Horizon Europe's requirements, it is strongly recommended that consortia involve their stakeholders as soon as possible in such a consulting body. The SAB members will provide constructive input and guidance on the project activities in order to maximize the visibility of the outputs and to achieve the project goals. Their opinions, although not binding for the consortium, will be highly considered by the consortium management.

We selected 3 external experts. In alphabetical order: Doug Crane, Jean-yves Escabasse, and Julie Hollis. They represent different stakeholders' sectors, from the minerals side to the thermoelectric industry, including R&D&I. We look forward to working with them in the next years and will introduce them to you one by one in this newsletter. In this issue, meet Julie Hollis (see in the relevant chapter)!

Figure 7 - The three members of START's Scientific Advisory Board. From left to right: Doug Crane, Jean-yves Escabasse, and Julie Hollis.

NEW EQUIPMENT ACQUIRED BY LNEG TO WORK ON START MATERIALS

In the framework of the project START, the following equipment were acquired by LNEG and are now in full operation:

- Vibratory Disc Mill "RS 200" and High Energy Ball Mill "Emax". The RS 200, which allows very short grinding times with excellent reproducibility, is being used for crushing mineral samples in WP2 activities. On the other hand, the Emax is being used to process the p-type and n-type thermoelectric materials in WP3. The Emax combines high frequency impact, intensive friction, controlled circular jar movements and an innovative integrated water-cooling system that allows a substantial reduction in the processing time for mechanical alloying as well as a better transformation rate when compared to conventional ball mills.

- "LZT-Meter" is being used for a full thermoelectrical characterization (WP4) of the developed materials. The system combines both a Laser flash and a Seebeck and Electric Resistivity Analyzer to measure the thermal diffusivity and the Seebeck Coefficient and the Electric Resistivity, respectively. The included software package provides the possibility to evaluate all measured data and to calculate the figure-of-merit, zT , which is a fundamental parameter to evaluate the thermoelectrical quality of the different processed materials. An extra device module was also purchased for a more direct determination of the zT (Harman method) allowing a rapid scanning of the materials under test.

Figure 8 - Retsch RS200 Vibratory Disc Mill.

Figure 9 - Retsch Emax High Energy Ball Mill.

Figure 10 - Linsels LZT-Meter.

START WEBINARS

Among dissemination activities, we are organising a series of free webinars. Have you taken part in our first events?

The first START webinar took place on 28th February, 14:30-15:30 CET. It was dedicated first of all to an overview about the project, given by our coordinator F. Neves, of LNEG, and then to a presentation by D. de Oliveira, also of LNEG, that covered the issue of collecting mineral samples in a uniform way from the mines. All that was followed by a question time. We had more than 60 participants and the full recording of the sessions is freely available on our website and on our YouTube channel: if you want to rewatch it, follow this link: <https://youtu.be/kblFV0B05aA>

Figure 11 - Advertisement of the 1st START webinar, held on 28th February 2023.

Figure 12 - Screenshot taken during the 1st START webinar on 28th February 2023.

The second START webinar was focused on Latin America, and took place on 26th April, 16:00-17:15 CEST. After a quick introduction by our coordinator, we had two speakers from important stakeholders in the area:

- Fredy Guzmán Martínez, head of Environmental Projects on the Servicio Geológico Mexicano (Mexican Geological Survey) and chief of the Mining Environmental Liabilities Expert Group of the Association of Iberoamerican Geological and Mining Surveys (ASGMI), who spoke about "Critical raw materials in mining environmental liabilities: A review".
- Rafael Bittencourt Lima, geological researcher at CPRM - Serviço Geológico do Brasil (Brazilian Geological Survey) who addressed the topic "Tetrahedrite as an accessory mineral in Brazilian mineral deposits".

At the end of the presentations, a few minutes of questions and answers closed the session. Participants were this time 30, including several interested attendees from a few American countries. Also this webinar is available for watching or rewatching here:

<https://youtu.be/m9hS7NNjOTw>.

Figure 13 - Advertisement of F. Guzmán Martínez (SGM) as speaker in the 2nd START webinar on 26th April 2023.

Figure 14 - Advertisement of R. Bittencourt Lima (SGB) as speaker in the 2nd START webinar on 26th April 2023.

A third event is scheduled, for the afternoon of 31st May, again at 14:30 CEST, and it will include presentations from European partners and experts, still related to the mining and minerals aspects of the project. A detailed agenda will be made public soon and registration for the event will be consequently opened. Stay tuned on our website and social media!

Figure 15 - Screenshot taken during the 2nd START webinar on 26th April 2023.

Figure 55: START-Newsletter_Issue_2-page-009

START AND GENDER BALANCE

Figure 16 - Three female members of the consortium were chosen to promote gender equality on the International Women Day.

In occasion of the International Women’s Day, 8th March 2023, we wanted to show that we care. We had just completed an internal review of the gender balance in our consortium, that showed some good data and yet, as more generally usual in the whole society, with room for improvement: in fact, 40% of the people involved in START are women, with 1 female Work Package leader, 5 task leaders, and 3 team leaders.

On that date, we published contributions from three of our female colleagues. One is the CV of Patricia Almeida Carvalho of SINTEF, who is leading the Workpackage 4 “Materials Characterization” in the project; and then 2 videos, one from Gracia Olivenza (ASGMI, Spain) and the other from Concepción Fernández Leyva (IGME-CSIC, Spain), both giving insight in the project and on their role in the activities. You can find all details on our website: <https://www.start-heproject.com/1350-2/>

START ON THE MAGAZINE “POWDER METALLURGY REVIEW”

An article written by our team (with contributions from F. Neves (LNEG), B. Vicenzi (EPMA), A. Bianchin (MBN Nanomaterialia), M. Rosinski (GeniCore) and H. Yin (TEGnology)) was published on the Spring 2023 issue (vol. 12, n.1) of the well-known powder metallurgical magazine Powder Metallurgy Review. On page 89, the paper titled “The START project: Creating a sustainable supply chain for green energy harvesting products by Powder Metallurgy” includes an overview of START’s motivation, approach, goals and expected impact, and, targeting the magazine’s usual audience within the powder metallurgy community, more details into the powder metallurgy side of the project: how to derive powders from the tetrahedrite containing minerals and pure elements (by Mechanochemical Synthesis), and how to consolidate them (by Pulse Plasma Compaction) into functional materials and devices with good thermoelectric properties. Some initial data and images coming from the ongoing tasks are shown.

The full issue is freely available for reading and downloading in pdf version on the Powder Metallurgy Review website:

<https://www.pm-review.com/powder-metallurgy-review-archive/powder-metallurgy-review-spring-2023-vol-12-no-1/>

We thank Powder Metallurgy Review and Inovar Communications Ltd for the attention given to our project!

Figure 17 - The first page of our article in the Spring 2023 issue of Powder Metallurgy Review.

www.START-HEproject.com 10 May 2023 DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7925963

Figure 56: START-Newsletter_Issue_2-page-010

START ON THE MAGAZINE “ÁGUA&AMBIENTE”

A Portuguese magazine dealing with the environment (energy, waste and water issues), “água & ambiente”, a magazine with about 1200 printed copies, hosted an article (in Portuguese) about our project in its November-December 2022 issue. The original title was “Projeto START vai transformar resíduos de minas em produtos para dispositivos termoeletricos” (“The START project will transform mine wastes into thermoelectric devices”). It is a detailed interview with our coordinator F. Neves (LNEG) that fills page 48 and 49 of the magazine.

Figure 18 - The START project featuring on “agua & ambiente” Nov-Dec 2022, pages 48-49.

START ON THE MAGAZINE “INGENIUM”

The magazine “Ingenium” published by the Ordem dos Engenheiros (the Portuguese Professional Public Association of Engineers), that is distributed to all members of that association (around 60000) hosted a short info, in Portuguese, about the project in its April-May-June 2023 issue n. 180, page 114. The main features of START were summarized and a link to our website was given.

Figure 19 - The news about START in Ingenium, n.180, p.114.

Figure 57: START-Newsletter_Issue_2-page-011

STARTY IN 12 LANGUAGES!

You already know Starty, that is usually the front “man” of our communication. To make Starty more widely understandable, we made the effort of covering a large part of the EU official languages, and even more. We have made our comics author J. Mascarenhas (LNEG) work hard to deliver new versions of his comic strip involving the robot Starty in twelve different languages! He received the contribution from many of our consortium partners, with the translation of the original Starty strip (that you have seen in Issue 1 of our newsletter) into their mother tongues. All in all, we have collected in the document that you can download from this link or from the Documents page the following languages: Danish, German, English, Spanish, French, Italian, Dutch, Norwegian, Polish, Portuguese, Slovakian, Turkish.

You can find the multilingual edition of “Starty explains START” on our website’s Documents page!

Figure 20 - Starty loves all languages!

START DISSEMINATION EVENTS

In the second part of the first year, START continued to take part in events with some of its consortium members.

PDAC 2023, The World’s Premier Mineral Exploration & Mining Convention, Toronto (Canada), 5th-8th March 2023

The project START was present at the PDAC (Prospectors and Developers Association of Canada) 2023 edition, which took place in the Toronto Convention Centre from 5th to 8th March. The event attracted almost 24000 attendees from 133 countries, 2500 investors, and hosted 1050 exhibitors.

Figure 21 - Delegates during a session at PDAC 2023 (from PDAC’s website).

Figure 22 - Exhibition at PDAC 2023 (from PDAC’s website).

A continuous presentation outlining the projects objectives and goals was shown during the event in the EU booth. This presentation generated interest amongst visitors to the booth.

Figure 23 - Left: Presentation about START on show at the PDAC 2023; right: the EU booth that hosted START.

ASGMI General Assembly Santo Domingo (Dominican Republic), 17th-21st April

ASGMI held its General Assembly from April 17th to 21st in Santo Domingo (Dominican Republic).

Figure 24 - Delegates at the ASGMI General Assembly 2023.

Figure 25 - G. Olivenza (ASGMI) at the ASGMI General Assembly 2023.

During the Assembly, a workshop was held on “The role of geological services in the ecological and energy transition,” and there were talks from the different participating geological services on the state of the art in the identification and characterization of critical minerals in their respective countries, among other topics.

The Vice President of the Government, Raquel Peña, and the Minister of Energy and Mines of the Dominican Republic attended the opening ceremony. Also, the Minister of Mining of Guatemala and representatives from international institutions that are not part of ASGMI, such as UNEP and USGS, joined the event.

During the talks, the activity report of ASGMI's expert groups was presented, specifically the groups on mining environmental liabilities and mineral resources participating in the START project. The project was discussed, the presentation video was shared, and the next webinar, the second START free webinar, which was held the following week, was announced.

International Conference “Sourcing the European energy transition from domestic resources – vision or wishful thinking”, Uppsala (Sweden), 25-26th April 2023

START was present also in this conference, hosted by the EU HORIZON 2020 project GREENPEG, in cooperation with the Swedish Association of Mines, Minerals and Metal Producers (SVEMIN) and the European Technology Platform on Sustainable Mineral Resources (ETP SMR) in Uppsala, in 25th-26th April. Some informative material and a rollup about the project were exhibited.

Figure 26 - The START rollup shown at the conference organised in Uppsala by the GREENPEG project.

Around 100 participants from all around the globe were attending the conference. Part of the conference was about topics regarding the EU's Green deal and how the actual geopolitical situation is affecting global supply chains. The START project attracted the interest of attendants based on the fact that waste material like domestically sourced tetrahedrite could fill gaps in those supply chains.

GREENPEG invited the START consortium to give more detailed information in the form of a webinar in the near future.

EPMA General Assembly 2023, Brussels and hybrid, 27th April 2023 – and other events

During the General Assembly of the European Powder Metallurgy Association (EPMA), F. Neves (LNEG) gave a thorough presentation of about 30' to present the project in detail, with a focus on the powder metallurgy content in the project, to address the interests of the audience, about 30 people consisting of members of the association and a few invited speakers. The event was held in a hybrid format on 27th April 2023, with some participants in Brussels (legal address of the EPMA), and some connected remotely. In addition to that, in the morning B. Vicenzi (EPMA) had showed in a slide the main features of the project whilst reviewing the activity of the association in EU funded projects.

Figure 27 - Screenshot taken during F. Neves presentation of the project in the EPMA General Assembly 2023.

Additionally, the two technical managers of EPMA have given information about the activities of START during the seminars held in early 2023, namely the Hot Isostatic Pressing seminar in Dresden (8th-9th March) and the Press&Sinter seminar in Barcelona (28th-29th March). In the latter occasion, some promotional materials about START (leaflet and the issue of Powder Metallurgy Review containing the article on the project) was also available to the about 25 delegates.

Figure 60: START-Newsletter_Issue_2-page-014

Figure 28 - Among the literature available for the EPMA seminar "Progress and Challenges in Press&Sinter" there was also the START flyer.

Future events

START is currently deciding which events to attend in the next months. For the moment we are thinking of:

- A training lecture on "Thermoelectric Materials and the START Project" is foreseen at the EPMA Powder Metallurgy Summer School that will take place in Dresden, at the Fraunhofer IFAM, from 17th to 21st July 2023
- A booth will be again prepared at the EPMA Euro PM2023 Congress & Exhibition that will be held in Lisbon, from 1st to 4th October 2023
- Plus, numerous other smaller events where project partners will bring information and short presentations about the project.

We will also repeat the participation in most or all of the events already covered in 2022. So maybe you will meet us in some of these events! Do not hesitate to get in touch directly!

TECHNICAL PILLS

TETRAHEDRITES IN THE WORLD

Tetrahedrite-(Zn) is a copper antimony sulfosalt mineral from the so called Tetrahedrite Group including Tetrahedrite, Tennantite, and Freibergite. Tetrahedrite with the formula $Cu_6(Cu_xZn_x)Sb_4S_{13}$ is the antimony end member of the continuous solid solution series with arsenic-bearing tennantite and the silver-rich variety Freibergite.

Mineral

The name of the mineral derives from its tetrahedron shaped cubic crystals with a density of 4.97 g/cm³. The colour of the mineral is steel grey to black metallic and a Mohs hardness of 3.5 – 4, comparable with Fluorite.

Figure 29 - Tetrahedrite Subgroup mineral from Georg Mine, Germany. Source: mindat.org

Tetrahedrite like other sulfosalts is an economic copper ore with an average copper content of 34.8 %. The silver rich Freibergite has a silver content up to 18 % and it was an important silver ore in the area of Freiberg in Saxony, Germany.

Figure 30 - Microscopy of an ore from Leogang, Austria. Qz: Quartz, Si: Siderite, Cp: Calcopryrite, Tn: Tennantite

Occurrences

Tetrahedrite occurs in low to moderate temperature hydrothermal veins and in some contact metamorphic deposits, associated with Arsenopyrite, Baryte, Bornite, Calcite, Dolomite, Fluorite, Galenite, Pyrite, Quartz, Siderite, and Sphalerite. Around 6000 occurrences around the world are documented.

Occurrences in Germany have been reported in Baden-Württemberg (e.g. near Freudenstadt), in Saxony (e.g. Erzgebirge), and in other places from Rhineland-Palatinate to e.g. North Rhine-Westphalia, Lower Saxony, and Saxony-Anhalt. In Austria, Kärnten, Salzburg Land, Steiermark and the area of Brixlegg in Tirol are the main places where Tetrahedrite occur and had been mined since Celtic times.

In Switzerland it is known from occurrences from Val d'Anniviers and Graubünden. The occurrence in the French Pyrenees is famous for their huge crystal size up to 25 cm. The famous Herodsfoot Mine of Lanreath, Liskeard District, Cornwall, England, has produced excellent crystals of this mineral, almost always associated with golden Chalcopyrite.

Peru has produced the finest Tetrahedrite crystals in a wide range of different localities, e.g., Casapalca or Mundo Nuevo Mine. Another important South American locality is the Machacamarca District in Bolivia. Bingham Canyon is an important locality in the US.

Figure 31 - Localities for Tetrahedrite (numbers), mining sites (mallet and Iron). For more details and a full legenda of symbols, refer to <https://www.mindat.org/min-3924.html>

POWDER METALLURGY OF TETRAHEDRITES

Powder technology is one of the processing technologies that are being used to produce mineral-derived p-type thermoelements. The approach followed in the START project is schematically summarized in Figure 32 and includes three main steps:

- 1) Direct synthesis of nanostructured powders of the mineral-derived p-type material by mechanochemical synthesis (MCS).
- 2) Consolidation of the powders produced in step 1 by pulse plasma compaction (PPC) to produce bulk materials.
- 3) Assembly and production of the TE devices incorporating the mineral-derived p-type thermoelements produced in step 2.

Figure 32 - The use of powder technology in START and main partners involved in this activity.

MCS, a solid-state synthesis route using high-energy ball mills and already in use for large-scale production by MBN[®], is a suitable and fast way to produce sulphide semiconductor powders^{7,8}. During the MCS process, the chemical reactivity is promoted under non-equilibrium conditions, near room temperature, by unbalanced mechanical forces with the transfer of the mechanical energy to the powder particles resulting in the introduction of strain into the powder, through the generation of dislocations and other defects that act as fast diffusion paths changing the reactivity of the powders⁸. Moreover, mechanical deformation occurs on a local basis, being mediated by dislocations and other lattice defects. As a result, the mass transport process will be reduced relative to that of high-temperature solid-state diffusion, with a great impact on the chemical and physical behaviour of the compounds. There are several variables which influence the MCS process, e.g., type of the mill, material of milling media, ball-to-powder ratio, filling extent of the milling chamber, milling atmosphere, milling speed, milling time, etc.⁸.

PPC is a modification of the conventional spark plasma sintering (SPS) process⁹. In PPC, the energy stored in a capacitor bank and charged to several kV, is delivered to the powder in short pulses of hundreds of μ s with a frequency up to 200 Hz, using the oscillating capacitor discharge to produce current surges with an amplitude of the first half-wave of several tens of kA. The high voltage and short pulses result in power values up to 80 MW and field-enhanced diffusivity enables full densification at lower temperature setpoints than in conventional SPS, where low-voltage electric fields are employed¹⁰. SPS-based technologies have proven to be a viable consolidation technique for sulphide-based powders to achieve a full-density compaction at temperatures considerably lower than the melting point allowing the nanostructures developed by the MCS process to be retained. Other advantages of SPS include fast-heating rate, short cycle time, accurate control of sintering energy, high reproducibility, safety and reliability.

The use in the START project of the innovative PPC device, and of the upgraded field assisted sintering technology (U-FAST), both developed by GeniCore, is expected to result in more appropriate densities and materials stability improvements preventing thermally induced solid-state reactions in the TE material during service, which will be beneficial for the overall TE performance. The production of square samples in place of the traditional cylindrical compacts will be assessed. From a technological point of view, this will represent a cost-effective solution and a huge step forward in the consolidation of parallelepiped thermoelements required for device assembly for large-scale applications.

Sulphur-based compounds are a vast class of materials, some of which are semiconductor materials with exceptional properties for energy conversion applications, either as thermoelectric materials or as photovoltaic materials^{7,11,12,13}. Among these, the tetrahedrite-tennantite series has the great advantage of being naturally occurring and often considered as waste by the mineral processing industries, as mentioned above.

Unfortunately, the thermoelectric properties of natural tetrahedrite-tennantite, and its thermal stability, are not good enough for commercial exploitation, because of the presence of other phases (i.e., farnatinite) and other minerals (e.g., pyrite, chalcopyrite, and quartz). The refinement of pure tetrahedrite-tennantite by conventional mining processes is not economically viable, but its direct use as raw material in the production of modified tetrahedrite-tennantite by powder technology processes is a promising route.

Figure 63: START-Newsletter_Issue_2-page-017

Tetrahedrite-tennantite powders can be obtained by solid-state processing route from the elements, with relatively small effort, but a more cost-efficient approach is to start from minerals with known composition and balance it with elemental powders. With this approach, minerals coming from different sites, hence with different compositions and structures, can be processed with a dedicated material balance, targeting the same thermoelectric performance.

At the laboratory level, the effectiveness of processing natural and synthetic tetrahedrites has been already demonstrated in the range of grams, and it is now scaled by a factor of x100, approaching a relevant pilot scale production.

With the support of the Lundin Mining Company, tetrahedrite-tennantite mineral from the Neves-Corvo mine (Portuguese zone of the Iberian Pyrite Belt) has been used, and it has been processed with 20%, 50% and 80% of synthetic tetrahedrite (Figure 33), testing two different processing routes. Both routes are based on industrial MCS apparatus using plants designed by MBN nanomaterialia spa¹⁴, which favours a direct transfer of impact energy to the processed material. The milling chamber is cooled to work near ambient temperature and the process is done in Argon atmosphere.

Figure 33 - Composition of the processed powder mixture with 20% of synthetic tetrahedrite.

The first route is more conservative; the synthetic tetrahedrite is formed previously in a different MCS process and then added to the natural mineral for the final mixing. The second route consists in a direct MCS of the natural mineral with the elemental copper, antimony and sulphur powders, balanced as in the first route for consistent benchmarking. This second route is more challenging but provides more flexibility when the attempt is more about alloying new elements into the tetrahedrite-tennantite rather than dispersing synthetic tetrahedrite into the natural-occurring one.

The backscattered electron images from Figure 34 do not reveal substantial differences between the material obtained in the two routes, not even at lower magnification as regards pyrite (dark grey) and quartz (darker spots) distribution.

Figure 34 - Typical backscattered electron images of the processed materials when starting from powder mixtures of: left image - mineral/synthetic tetrahedrite (first route), right image - mineral/elemental powders (second route).

Typical X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns for some of the processed materials are shown in Figure 35. The XRD patterns confirm that the two routes are consistent with each other; a small difference appears in the famatinite peak, which is promoted when processed directly from powders mixtures containing elemental powders. This is a positive result since it confirms that the two routes are equally effective, and it opens the way for the direct processing via MCS of natural tetrahedrite-tennantite material with metals and sulphur powders for the production of thermoelectric materials.

Figure 35 - (a) Typical XRD patterns of the mineral and some of the processed materials. (b) Typical XRD patterns for doped synthetic tetrahedrite as function of the MCS energy level.

The formation of famatinite, which is an unwanted phase, is due to the lack of stabilizing elements such as Fe and Zn as substitutes of Cu in the synthetic tetrahedrite utilized in the experiment. In fact, the synthesis of doped tetrahedrite reduces the formation of famatinite when higher MCS energy levels are used (Figure 35). This synthesis has been done in industrial plants to validate the feasibility of the approach. The next development steps are therefore related to the identification of the most effective combination of substitutional elements that will be used as a reference target in the processing of minerals with metals and sulphur powder.

This approach will enable the enhancement of naturally occurring tetrahedrite-tennantite to make it an effective thermoelectric material and has the potential to be transferred to other combinations of minerals and metals for the synthesis of functional materials.

MEET THE SCIENTIFIC ADVISORY BOARD MEMBERS

In the next issues, we will present you the members of our Scientific Advisory Board. We will do that by means of short interviews where they will highlight their activity and the activity of their institutions and companies. We start with Julie Hollis, Secretary General of the EuroGeoSurveys.

Julie HOLLIS (EuroGeoSurveys)

Figure 36 - Julie Hollis is Secretary General of EuroGeoSurveys (EGS) – The Geological Surveys of Europe – a geoscience liaison point with the European Commission, EU institutions, and other stakeholders including academia, industry, and professional associations. Her focus is steering EGS toward becoming a sustainable Geological Service for Europe, supporting the EU's green energy and digital transition. Previously, Julie led the Department of Geology for the Ministry of Mineral Resources in Nuuk, Greenland, and has also worked for 3 geological survey organizations in Australia and Denmark, managing regional geoscience mapping programs. Julie has a BSc from the University of Sydney, and PhD in Geology and Master of Science Communication and Public Engagement from the University of Edinburgh

What are the mission and objectives of the EuroGeoSurveys (EGS) and how do you work to accomplish them?

EuroGeoSurveys is a not-for-profit organisation representing 37 Geological Surveys of Europe. We provide the European Institutions, regulators, industry, and the public, with expert, balanced and practical pan-European geoscience data and advice to guide policy and to address key societal challenges, supporting the EU's competitiveness, social well-being, environmental management and international commitments.

We do this by coordinating the network of the Geological Surveys of Europe and through the collaborative research and activities of our Expert Groups and Task Forces. Through our European Geological Data Infrastructure (Figure 38), we provide open-access, harmonised geological maps, and data to inform EU, local and national policy, and for the benefit of all European citizens.

Our vision is to establish a unified Geological Service for Europe based on a common European Geological Knowledge Base.

Figure 37 - Excerpts from the EGS website.

How is EGS contributing to the EU priorities related with the application of the European Green Deal and the EU Action Plan on Critical Raw Materials?

At the heart of the collaboration between the Geological Surveys of Europe is our ambition to establish a sustainable Geological Service for Europe, serving European society through, and beyond, the green transition.

Through a five-year Coordination and Support Action, the Geological Service for Europe project (GSEU), EuroGeoSurveys will deliver a plan for a sustainable Geological Service for Europe to be implemented beyond the 2027 project end. This service will serve European society and inform sound policy in water, energy, raw materials, hazards, and all areas that require subsurface data and expertise. Through this service, we will contribute to environmental sustainability and social well-being in Europe, supported by a powerful and comprehensive digital infrastructure and a strong network of geoscience experts.

EuroGeoSurveys and our member Geological Surveys of Europe play a key role in the EU Action Plan on Critical Raw Materials. EGS has a long history of collaborative research (e.g., ProMine, Minerals4EU, euRare, SCREEN, and GeoERA, including the FRAME project) and science for policy advice regarding CRMs. This is continued, compiled, and expanded within GSEU project.

Figure 38 - European Geological Data Infrastructure (EGDI) website: map of all Critical Raw Materials resources occurrences in Europe¹⁵.

What strategies can be adopted to improve the sustainability of Europe's raw material value chains, and in particular to fuel the European energy transition with domestic resources?

There is much to be done to build EU resilience in regard to CRM security. A comprehensive framework for supporting the whole CRM value chain has recently been outlined in the proposed CRM Act. Developing domestic supply is a crucial component of the required work and both primary and secondary resources will be important. Our work currently underway within the Geological Service for Europe Project builds on many previous projects and expertise gained to provide services and knowledge to increase sourcing of primary and secondary CRMs in Europe and decrease import dependency. This includes establishment of an International Centre of Excellence on Sustainable Resource Management supported by UNFC and UNRMS expertise, an atlas of primary and secondary CRM resources in Europe, including potential and favourability maps. The expertise of the European Geological Surveys is recognised in the proposed CRM Act, which mandates the national surveys to carry out national programmes of geological data acquisition, processing, and delivery to promote CRM exploration investment in Europe. This data and knowledge acquisition and delivery will be a key driver in the discovery and development of future CRM resources in Europe.

What is the position of the EGS concerning the Horizon Europe Framework Programme for Research and Innovation?

EGS recognises the importance of the EU Framework Programmes for Research and Innovation in developing excellent research and fostering pan-European as well as international collaboration activities in support of the European Research Area. EGS has a long history of engagement in the Framework Programmes, mainly through the collaboration of its members and Expert Groups and more recently with the involvement of the organisation itself in a number of key strategic projects aimed at pooling the expertise and knowledge available within the national Geological Surveys in support of EU policy priorities, namely through the GeoERA ERA-Net programme, addressing the themes of geoenergy, groundwater, raw materials, and an information platform, and now the GSEU project. The Framework Programmes not only offer the opportunity to collaborate across borders, but also the ability to cluster with other relevant and complimentary research projects and reach out to stakeholder communities not always available at national level, boosting the potential impact of the research being undertaken. This has been important for EGS in growing our network and opening relations with new partners.

What is the aspect of the START project that you find more appealing, and why?

The START project is an excellent example of research and innovation that covers the full spectrum from basic to applied research through to pilot implementation and scaling up, in the process also building expert networks across public and private sectors, government, academia and industry. From an EGS perspective, our CRM experts are largely focussed on the upstream end of the value chain and while we aim to support sound science-based decision making that will have positive impact at the downstream end, we rely on our stakeholders and partners to have a greater engagement at this other end of the spectrum. START provides a valuable opportunity for building these networks and for identifying and addressing roadblocks through collaborative cross-sectoral research and innovation efforts.

Where do you see the best chances of synergies between EGS and START?

EGS has a wealth of data and expertise on European primary and secondary CRM resources and potential. A key point of intersection between EGS and START will be in linking the findings of START in relation to the most suitable mine wastes for the thermoelectric technology with the EGS expertise on Europe's secondary mineral resources. These secondary mineral resources are a focus of the current GSEU project and will be an area of increasing focus for the Geological Surveys of Europe as they plan for providing data and knowledge needed to implement the future CRM Act.

Thanks Julie!

CONSORTIUM TOUR

We continue our tour of consortium members: in this issue, two industrial partners that are already active in the thermoelectric device market. Meet TEGnology (Denmark) and RGS (the Netherlands).

TEGNOLOGY

TEGNOLOGY

TEGnology ApS is one of START's industrial partners, who is specialized in developing thermoelectric generators (TEGs) with advanced thermoelectric materials and novel module design. As a DeepTech Danish startup company, we provide more sustainable and cost-efficient TEGs, and expand our business to customized self-powered IoT devices. TEGnology has substantiated its new design (World Patent: WO2023031269A1) of a flexible TEG module (Flex-TEG®) in 2022 and started production thereafter. The company's business is to develop and sell cost-efficient and endurance TEGs as well as providing consultancy services in this field. Its potential is to provide TEG components for self-powered IoT devices, which are in large demand for many application areas such as smart construction/buildings, industrial factories, power plants, private homes, etc. Our products have been sold to end users including Novo Nordisk, Alfa Laval, Novozymes, etc.

In the START project, TEGnology will use the expertise to demonstrate that the new mineral-derived tetrahedrite p-type thermoelement, can be fabricated in a production relevant environment and integrated with commercial TE devices with system design in a cost-efficient way. On the other hand, TEGnology will help to identify the suitable n-type thermoelectric materials for matching the p-type mineral-derived sulphides compositions.

www.tegnology.dk

Figure 67: START-Newsletter_Issue_2-page-021

RGS DEVELOPMENT

RGS Development is a technology company, promoting advanced silicon materials and devices for static power generation. Located in Broek op Langedijk (The Netherlands), a team of highly skilled employees are developing thermal electric materials and remote power solutions, supporting the global drive in the sustainable energy transition.

RGS development is founded by Energy Research Centre of the Netherlands (ECN) in 2000 initially to produce pSi wafers for Solar PV. Since 2013 the company has expended their activities around the application of Silicon in power generation and storage. Under the brand name Thermagy it operates the design and manufacturing of silicon germanium based thermoelectric materials and thermoelectric solutions. Under the brand name Solwafer it develops and manufacturers advanced silicon components for next generations of solar pv and thermophotovoltaics. Furthermore, it serves as technology provider for E-magy (www.e-magy.com), which introduces nano porous silicon for the next generation Li-ion batteries.

RGS development participates in a growing number of projects related to remote power generation in various industries such as Aerospace and Security and Combined Heat and Power generation (CHP). RGS provides expertise and knowledge on Silicon and the manufacturing of thermoelectric devices, for projects such as Integral, Sparc-ee, Wraps, and Next Gen RTG programs.

RGS development contributes in the START project a large expertise on the production of silicon-based materials (including TE materials, e.g., Si1-xGex) by a proprietary casting process technology (the Ribbon Growth on Substrate), and on designing and engineering TE devices for waste heat recovery systems and combined heat and power (CHP) systems. It will use its casting technology for producing the mineral-derived tetrahedrite p-type, in WP3, and will provide the n-type Si1-xGex. It will lead WP5 and will use its fully in house manufacturing capability for TE devices to adapt the Thermagy™ device to incorporate and validate the RGS-cast mineral-derived tetrahedrite p-type thermoelement. RGS will prepare for and anticipate on the integration of the TE devices into CHP and Waste Heat Recovery applications.

www.rgsdevelopment.nl

Figure 68: START-Newsletter_Issue_2-page-022

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CONTACTS

START regularly updates its website and social media with news about its activities, but also with more general documents and info on the topics of relevance for the project. Thermoelectricity, waste heat recovery, mine waste remining, sustainability, raw materials and critical raw materials, energy efficiency, and many others.

If you are interested in receiving this newsletter and other special news from the project directly in your mailbox, consider subscribing our mailing list on the website (“Contacts” page, “subscribe” section)! Clicking on the “Subscribe” button, you will fill a form generated by SendinBlue, our mailing system, and will subsequently receive an E-Mail to confirm your address. Your data will be treated and stored in accordance with the EU GDPR Regulation. And do not forget to follow all our social media accounts! Here is the list of the important links to click to reach our news:

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Twitter: https://twitter.com/START_HEproject

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Figure 69: START-Newsletter_Issue_2-page-023

11 ANNEX II – ARTICLE ON POWDER METALLURGY REVIEW, SPRING 2023 ISSUE

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START project

The START project: Creating a sustainable supply chain for green energy harvesting products by Powder Metallurgy

Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling (START) is an Innovation Action project co-funded by the EU and its Horizon Europe programme. Using an advanced powder production and consolidation process, the project's aim is to create a sustainable supply chain for green energy harvesting products by transforming sulphide materials from mining waste into sustainable high-added-value Powder Metallurgy components for tellurium-free thermoelectric (TE) devices. Here, the consortium members offer a comprehensive summary of START's background, the innovative workflow developed, and its potential impact.

Launched in June 2022, the START project is formed of a consortium of fifteen institutions from eleven European countries, coordinated by LNEG - the National Laboratory of Energy and Geology of Portugal. Six research organisations with backgrounds in geology, materials science and renewable energies are represented on the consortium, as well as seven SMEs covering the entire supply chain, from production to exploitation and ecological footprint assessment, and two non-profit international associations representing a consolidated network of partners and stakeholders. START will have a duration of four years and a budget of around €9.2 million. Fig. 1 identifies the consortium partners and participating nations.

Motivation and objective

Climate change is one of humankind's greatest challenges, and fighting it depends on the rapid implementation of green technol-

ogies and business practices, known as the green transition, to which the European Union (EU) is fully committed through the European Green Deal [1]. However, this green transition is based on a shift from a fossil fuel-inten-

sive to a material-intensive energy system, increasing the need for mineral resources. The growing demand for essential minerals and declining quality of ores is substantial increasing waste volumes from mining operations.

Fig. 1 START consortium members and the nations they represent

Figure 70: START article on the Spring 2023 issue of Powder Metallurgy Review (page 89).

Fig. 2 The START concept is based on a 'waste material-waste heat to power' methodology

Additionally, current commercial thermoelectric (TE) generators (used to harvest waste heat from, for example, industrial processes and convert it into electric power) rely mostly on tellurium-based thermoelements [2]. Tellurium is a relatively scarce element, with a terrestrial abundance of Ca. 1 ppb. As China accounts for over 60% of its production, Europe is heavily dependent on imports [3].

The START project proposes a unique technological solution to this problem, based on a 'waste material-waste heat to power' methodology for the development of sustainable and economically viable tellurium-free TE waste heat harvesting systems (Fig. 2). This is

achieved by producing advanced sulphide p-type thermoelements that incorporate discarded sulphide minerals in mining waste, mainly of the tetrahedrite-tennantite mineral series $(\text{Cu}_2[\text{Cu}_2(\text{TM})_2](\text{Sb}, \text{As})_2\text{S}_4)$, where TM is a transition metal) to replace the current commercial tellurium-based p-type thermoelements. The tetrahedrite-tennantite mineral series is relatively abundant in some Cu mine tailings and, at present, is an environmental hazard.

START's development of green energy harvesting devices through the incorporation of mineral-derived p-type thermoelements serves both economic and remediation purposes by reducing

mining's environmental footprint, as mining residues are converted into useful and valuable resources. This strategy is in line with the priorities set out by the European Green Deal and the EU Action Plans on Critical Raw Materials and Circular Economy [1, 4, 5].

Potential impact of the START project

Around two-thirds of the primary energy produced worldwide is lost as waste heat [6]. Using TE energy harvesting systems to capture and directly convert this waste heat into electric power has the potential to improve overall energy production efficiency and, in conserving more of the energy produced, thus preventing tens of millions of tons of CO_2 emissions.

The impact of the START project's approach towards a more sustainable and resilient EU is defined as:

1. The reduction of EU dependence on primary critical raw materials
2. The promotion of circular economy processes
3. The production of TE energy harvesting systems focused

"... using TE energy harvesting systems to capture and directly convert this waste heat into electric power has the potential to improve overall energy production efficiency and [...] avoid tens of millions of tons of CO_2 emissions."

Figure 71: START article on the Spring 2023 issue of Powder Metallurgy Review (page 90).

Fig. 3 The START project's main outcomes for the value chain, European mineral resources market, and green economy

on increasing the overall efficiency of energy production and consumption systems, thereby reducing greenhouse gas emissions

The main outcomes of the project are outlined in Fig 3.

Powder Metallurgy in START

Powder Metallurgy is one of the processing technologies being used to produce the mineral-derived p-type thermoelements upon which the START project's success depends. The approach followed in the START project includes three main process steps, summarised in Fig. 4.

Production of nanostructured powders by Mechanochemical Synthesis

Mechanochemical Synthesis (MCS), comprising the first process step in the START approach, is a solid-state synthesis route which uses high-energy ball mills and is already in use for large-scale nanostructured powder production by MBN [7]. The process is a suitable and fast way to produce sulphide semiconductor powders from minerals and pure elements [8, 9].

During MCS, chemical reactivity is promoted under non-equilibrium conditions, near room temperature, by unbalanced mechanical forces that transfer the mechanical energy to the powder particles. This introduces strain into the powder by generating dislocations and other defects that act as fast diffusion paths, changing the reactivity of the powders [9].

Mechanical deformation also occurs on a local basis, being mediated by dislocations and other lattice defects. As a result, the mass-transport process will be reduced relative to that of high-temperature solid-state diffusion, having a great impact on the chemical and physical behaviour of the compounds. There are several variables which influence the MCS process (e.g. type of mill, milling media, ball-to-powder ratio, filling extent of the milling chamber, milling atmosphere, milling speed, milling time, etc.) [9].

Powder consolidation by Pulse Plasma Compaction

Pulse Plasma Compaction (PPC), a method developed by GeniCore, is used to consolidate the TE materials. This technology is a modification of the conventional spark plasma sintering (SPS) process [10]. In PPC,

energy stored in a capacitor bank and charged to several kV (in the SPS process, it is typically several volts), is delivered to the powder in profoundly shorter pulses than are used in SPS technology (dozens of us instead of a few ms) with a frequency up to 200 Hz.

Oscillating capacitor discharge is used to produce current pulses with a first half-wave amplitude of several tens of kA. The high voltage short pulses result in peak power values up to 80 MW, and field-enhanced diffusivity enables full densification at lower temperature setpoints than in conventional SPS, where low-voltage electric fields are employed [11].

SPS-based technologies have proven to be a viable consolidation technique to enable sulphide-based powders to achieve full-density compaction at temperatures considerably lower than their melting points, preserving the nanostructures developed by the MCS process [12]. Other advantages of SPS include a fast heating rate, short cycle time, accurate control of sintering energy, high reproducibility, safety and reliability.

The use of the innovative PPC device in the START approach, as

Figure 72: START article on the Spring 2023 issue of Powder Metallurgy Review (page 91).

Fig. 4 The START process workflow. The main partners involved in these activities are nanostructured powder specialist MBN Nanomaterialia, for Step 1; material engineering company GeniCore, Step 2; and TEGnology, a leading company in TE energy harvesting, Step 3.

well as the upgraded field-assisted sintering technology (U-FAST) developed by GeniCore, is expected to enable TE materials to be produced with more appropriate densities and improved material stability, preventing thermally induced solid-state reactions in the material during service, which will enhance overall TE performance.

The production of square samples instead of traditional cylindrical compacts will also be assessed. From a technological point of view, this could represent a cost-effective solution and a huge step forward in

the consolidation of parallelepiped thermoelements required for device assembly for large-scale applications.

Mineral-derived tetrahedrite powders produced by MCS

Sulphur-based compounds are a vast class of materials, some of which are semiconductor materials with exceptional properties for energy conversion applications, either as thermoelectric materials or as photovoltaic materials [8, 12–14]. Among

these, the tetrahedrite-tennantite series offers the great advantage of being naturally occurring.

Unfortunately, the poor thermoelectric properties and low thermal stability of natural tetrahedrite-tennantite – caused by the presence of other phases (i.e., farnatinitite) and other minerals (e.g., pyrite, chalcopyrite, and quartz) – restrict its use for commercial exploitation. The refinement of pure tetrahedrite-tennantite by conventional mining processes is not economically viable, but its direct use as a raw material in the production of modified tetrahedrite-tennantite by Powder Metallurgy is a promising route.

Tetrahedrite-tennantite powders can be produced from the elements by a relatively low-effort solid-state processing route, but a more cost-efficient approach is to start from minerals with known composition and balance them with elemental powders. Using this approach, minerals from different sites, and hence with different compositions and structures, can be processed with a dedicated material balance, targeting the same thermoelectric performance.

“The refinement of pure tetrahedrite-tennantite by conventional mining processes is not economically viable, but its direct use as a raw material in the production of modified tetrahedrite-tennantite by PM is a promising route.”

Figure 73: START article on the Spring 2023 issue of Powder Metallurgy Review (page 92).

At the laboratory level, the effectiveness of processing natural and synthetic tetrahedrites has already been demonstrated in the range of grams [8]. It is now scaled by a factor of 100, approaching a relevant pilot-scale production.

Processing routes

With the support of the Lundin Mining Company, tetrahedrite-tennantite mineral from the Neves-Corvo mine (in the Portuguese sector of the Iberian Pyrite Belt) has been used. This material has been processed with purity levels of 20%, 50%, and 80% synthetic tetrahedrite (Fig. 5), via two different processing routes.

Both routes use industrial MCS apparatus, in plants designed by MBN Nanomaterialia Spa [6], which favours a direct transfer of impact energy to the processed material. The process is carried out in an argon atmosphere, with the milling chamber being cooled to operate near ambient temperature.

The first route is more conservative; the synthetic tetrahedrite is formed in a different MCS process and then added to the natural mineral for the final mixing. The second route consists of direct MCS of the natural mineral using the same composition of elemental

Fig. 5 Composition of the processed powder mixture with 20% of synthetic tetrahedrite

copper, antimony, and sulphur powders as was used in the first route, for consistent benchmarking.

This second route is more challenging but provides more flexibility, allowing a focus on alloying new elements into the tetrahedrite-tennantite rather than dispersing synthetic tetrahedrite into the naturally occurring one. The backscattered electron images in Fig. 6 show material obtained by both routes. The images do not reveal substantial differences between the results, even at higher magnification, regarding the distribution of pyrite (dark grey) and quartz (darker spots) distribution.

Typical X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns for some of the processed materials are shown in Fig. 7, top. These XRD patterns confirm that the two routes are consistent with each other; a small difference appears in the famatinite peak, which is promoted when processed directly from powders mixtures containing elemental powders.

This is a positive result, since it confirms that the two routes are equally effective, and it opens the way for the direct processing via MCS of natural tetrahedrite-tennantite material with metals and sulphur powders to produce thermoelectric materials.

Fig. 6 Typical backscattered electron images of the processed materials when starting from powder mixtures of (a) mineral/synthetic tetrahedrite (first route), and (b) mineral/elemental powders (second route)

Figure 74: START article on the Spring 2023 issue of Powder Metallurgy Review (page 93).

Fig. 7 Top: Typical XRD patterns of the mineral and some of the processed materials, Bottom: Typical XRD patterns for doped synthetic tetrahedrite as a function of the MCS energy level

The formation of famatinite, an unwanted phase, is due to the lack of stabilising elements such as Fe and Zn as substitutes for Cu in the synthetic tetrahedrite utilised in the experiment. The synthesis of doped tetrahedrite reduces the formation of famatinite when higher MCS energy levels are used (Fig. 7, bottom). This synthesis has been carried out in industrial plants to validate the feasibility of the approach. The next developmental steps are related to the identification of the most effective combination of substitutional elements that will be used as a reference target in the processing of minerals with metals and sulphur powder.

This approach will enable the enhancement of naturally occurring tetrahedrite-tennantite to make it an effective thermoelectric material and has the potential to be transferred to other combinations of minerals and metals for the synthesis of functional materials.

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Additional information

In the near future, START will organise several free webinars to provide more details on the project and offer updates on its activities. To stay informed, subscribe to the START mailing list.

www.start-heproject.com
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Figure 76: START article on the Spring 2023 issue of Powder Metallurgy Review (page 95).

12 ANNEX III – ARTICLE ON “AGUA & AMBIENTE” NOV-DEC 2022

resíduos

PROJETO START VAI TRANSFORMAR RESÍDUOS DE MINAS EM PRODUTOS PARA DISPOSITIVOS TERMOELÉTRICOS

O CONSÓRCIO MULTIDISCIPLINAR, COORDENADO PELO LABORATÓRIO NACIONAL DE ENERGIA E GEOLOGIA, ENVOLVE 15 INSTITUIÇÕES DE 11 PAÍSES EUROPEUS.

O conceito do projeto START – Sustainable Energy Harvesting Systems Based on Innovative Mine Waste Recycling envolve a transformação de resíduos disponíveis em escombros de minas em matérias-primas secundárias para serem utilizadas no desenvolvimento de dispositivos termoelétricos, que convertem calor residual em energia elétrica. Iniciado em junho deste ano e com uma duração prevista de quatro anos, o projeto, coordenado pelo Laboratório Nacional de Energia e Geologia (LNEG) visa, assim, criar uma cadeia de valor sustentável que não só garante uma utilização mais eficiente de recursos que atualmente são descartados como resíduos, como também contribui para a diversificação de fontes de energia sustentável, em linha com os objetivos do Pacto Ecológico Europeu.

No centro do projeto está a tetraedrite, um tipo específico de minério que resulta da mineração do cobre e que está amplamente disponível em vários países da Europa, incluindo Portugal, Espanha, Áustria e Eslováquia. A transição energética na Europa implica uma mudança de sistemas de energia baseados na utilização de combustíveis fósseis para sistemas de energia envolvendo uma utilização intensiva de materiais, contextualiza o coordenador do projeto, Filipe Neves. O aumento da procura por estes recursos irá conduzir “a uma diminuição da qualidade dos minérios”, mas também a “um aumento substancial nos volumes de resíduos da exploração mineira, incluindo estes minérios que têm interesse para este tipo de aplicação”, concretiza. A utilização direta de minério de tetraedrite, recolhido em escombros de minas abandonadas, no desenvolvimento de dispositivos termoelétricos vem, desde logo, dar uma vida nova a estes recursos, promovendo uma economia mais circular e um uso eficiente dos recursos disponíveis no espaço europeu.

Por seu lado, os dispositivos termoelétricos que se pretende desenvolver com base neste minério permitem converter o calor residual em energia elétrica e, também aqui, há um enorme potencial a explorar. Quase todos os processos industriais, bem como os equipamentos eletrónicos, envolvem a geração de calor: calcula-se que, em média, cerca de dois terços da energia primária produzida seja desperdiçada sob a forma de calor (ver figura). “A quantidade de calor residual que está disponível é imensa”, sublinha Filipe Neves, e “este calor pode ser reaproveitado, através dos dispositivos termoelétricos, para a produção de energia elétrica”. Só na União Europeia, o potencial de recuperação de calor residual em instalações industriais foi estimado em 300 a 350 TWh/ano, segundo um estudo publicado em 2019.

Ainda assim, a utilização de dispositivos termoelétricos não tem surgido em primeiro plano na estratégia da União Europeia para minimizar a dependência de combustíveis fósseis e tornar o sistema energético mais sustentável. Apesar de notar que a eficiência dos

sistemas termoelétricos não é muito elevada, Filipe Neves considera, contudo, que “faz todo o sentido [estes] serem utilizados, pensando na sustentabilidade, a nível geral, do sistema energético”, isto porque ao permitirem o reaproveitamento energético do calor residual, estes dispositivos oferecem um campo de aplicação muito amplo, nomeadamente na indústria pesada ou marítima (em navios de longo curso, por exemplo), mas também em dispositivos eletrónicos. As centrais de processamento de dados, por exemplo, “produzem uma quantidade enorme de calor”, ilustra Filipe Neves, e, através

destes sistemas, podem tornar-se “autosustentáveis em termos de energia”, porque “esse calor pode ser reaproveitado para produzir energia para o funcionamento desses próprios sistemas”.

O desenvolvimento da cadeia de valor sustentável proposta no projeto START pode assim ajudar também a “aumentar a eficiência geral dos sistemas de produção e de consumo de energia”, resume o investigador do LNEG, minimizando o consumo de combustíveis fósseis e contribuindo para a redução das emissões de gases com efeito de estufa.

MINIMIZAR DEPENDÊNCIA EXTERNA

A utilização de tetraedrite para o desenvolvimento destes dispositivos traz benefícios adicionais.

Atualmente, a maioria dos dispositivos termoelétricos disponíveis no mercado são compostos à base de bismuto ou chumbo de telúrio, um elemento que tem de ser importado de países asiáticos, em particular da China, onde está concentrada a sua produção. Algo que não acontece com a tetraedrite: “é um minério que não tem os problemas de localização geográfica que outros minérios têm”, nota Filipe Neves, dado que “está presente na Europa e, basicamente, nos cinco continentes”.

O desenvolvimento de dispositivos termoelétricos em telúrio, previsto no projeto, contribui assim para minimizar a dependência da União Europeia de matérias-primas que não existem dentro das suas fronteiras, ao mesmo tempo que facilita o aproveitamento de um material amplamente disponível em vários Estados-membros.

Além disso, uma análise comparada de sistemas termoelétricos baseados em tetraedrite com as soluções mais convencionais disponíveis no mercado evidencia que estes oferecem vantagens, não só em termos de disponibilidade de matérias-primas, mas também em aspetos ambientais. Por outro lado, estes dispositivos afirmam-se competitivos com outras opções, ao nível da temperatura necessária para a sua operação ou da facilidade de produção em larga escala, por exemplo.

Na utilização da tetraedrite num ecossistema de energia renovável termoelétrica, vai-se procurar fazer “o mínimo de processamento” possível do minério, desde logo para evitar a produção de mais resíduos. “A opção será tentar utilizar, na medida do possível, quase o minério tal e qual como vai ser recolhido”, esclarece o coordenador do projeto.

Para além de se incentivar a economia circular, por via da utilização de resíduos da exploração mineira, está ainda prevista a realização, no âmbito do projeto START, de um estudo de avaliação do ciclo de vida dos próprios dispositivos termoelétricos, para procurar afeitar oportunidades de reutilização de todos os componentes, no fim da sua vida útil.

• **Projeto START pretende criar uma cadeia de valor sustentável, que contribui para promover a economia circular e um sistema energético mais sustentável.**

• **No centro do projeto está a tetraedrite, que resulta da mineração do cobre e que está amplamente disponível em vários países da Europa, incluindo Portugal.**

• **Dispositivos termoelétricos permitem converter o calor residual em energia elétrica e têm um amplo campo de utilização, nomeadamente na indústria.**

“A opção será tentar utilizar, na medida do possível, quase o minério tal e qual como vai ser recolhido”, esclarece Filipe Neves

Figure 77: The START project featuring on “agua & ambiente” Nov-Dec 2022, page 48.

VALIDAR CONCEITO E ABRIR CAMINHO AO MERCADO

Apesar dos próximos quatro anos, pretende-se "validar o conceito" proposto no projeto, resume Filipe Neves, que em termos de viabilidade técnica, que econômica, isto permite também abrir caminho a novas oportunidades de mercado e ao desenvolvimento de um ecossistema comercial, em torno da transformação de resíduos em matérias-primas de elevado valor acrescentado, mas também da produção de sistemas termoelétricos sem telúrio, tendo presente os compromissos ambiciosos assumidos pela União Europeia para promover um sistema energético mais amigo do ambiente. O desenvolvimento do projeto poderá assim "atrair novos investidores que estejam interessados em explorar estas oportunidades", salienta o investigador. O consórcio multidisciplinar coordenado pelo LNEG agrega um total de 15 organizações de 11 países europeus (Portugal, Alemanha, Áustria, Bélgica, Dinamarca, Eslováquia, Espanha, Holanda, Itália, Noruega, Polónia). Entre os parceiros portugueses do projeto, inclui-se ainda a consultora 3 Diverso – Engenharia, Inovação e Ambiente.

A primeira fase do projeto, atualmente em curso, contempla a definição dos locais mais adequados para a recolha do minério, bem como a sua recolha e caracterização. "É uma fase importante", nota Filipe Neves, porque a utilização da tetraedrite "é a base do projeto". Em Portugal, Ajustrel e Neves-Corvo são alguns dos locais onde está prevista a recolha de tetraedrite em escombros de minas. As fases posteriores envolvem o processamento dos materiais, bem como o desenvolvimento, produção e avaliação de desempenho dos dispositivos termoelétricos.

O projeto START foi apoiado ao abrigo do programa comunitário Horizonte Europa com um financiamento superior a 2,6 milhões de euros. A sua conclusão está prevista para maio de 2026.

JOANA FELIPE

START - SUSTAINABLE ENERGY HARVESTING SYSTEMS BASED ON INNOVATIVE MINE WASTE RECYCLING

Fonte: LNEG, 2022

Coordenação:
LNEG

Consórcio multidisciplinar:
15 instituições de 11 países Europeus (Portugal, Alemanha, Áustria, Bélgica, Dinamarca, Eslováquia, Espanha, Holanda, Itália, Noruega, Polónia)

Cluster 4: Digital, Indústria e Espaço.
Índice HORIZON-CL4-2021-RESILIENCE-01-07 (Colaborando cadeias de valor inovadoras das matérias-primas e produtos sustentáveis)

Duração: 48 meses
(1 Janeiro 2022 - 31 maio 2026)

Total do custos elegíveis:
9 194 441,25 €

Financiamento máximo:
7 007 678,00 €

EGEO

RENOVAMOS PARA O FUTURO

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Figure 78: The START project featuring on “agua & ambiente” Nov-Dec 2022, page 49.